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D1.1 – Methods for PFAS in waters and complex matrices

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Executive Summary

This document is the result of Task 1.1 of WP1 of the PROMISCES project and includes the results of Subtasks 1.1.1 and 1.1.2.

Today, PFAS can be detected in almost all areas of the environment, requiring several different approaches to cover PFAS analysis in various sample matrices. This document is intended to help select appropriate methods for PFAS analysis in variable analytical conditions: Depending on the target PFAS-substances, the limits of quantification, and the matrix as well as the technical requirements of the laboratory, a suitable method can be selected.

In the methods described here for liquid matrices such as drinking water, groundwater and surface water, the focus is on the lowest possible limits of quantification. Due to potential direct exposure to humans, the methods for these matrices may be most relevant for monitoring by authorities. In addition, European legislation for these matrices such as the Drinking Water Directive (EU Directive 2020/2184) or recommendations such as EFSA's scientific opinion on selected PFAS-compounds provides specifications that must be followed.

The analytical methods for wastewater and landfill leachate need special purification steps due to the complexity of these matrices. There is also a need for special sample preparation in the methods that examine solid phases like sewage sludge and sediment. In these matrices the PFAS must be extracted from the solid material before being quantifiable. To identify PFAS sources in the circular economy such as industrial emissions in urban water cycles, quantification in complex matrices is of great relevance for environmental and human health.

A comparative summary of all methods discussed is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparative summary of all methods; for abbreviations, see Table 2.

	ACEA 1	ACEA 2	BRGM IPGP 1	BRGM IPGP 2	BWB 1	BWB 2	CSIC 1	CSIC 2	TU Wien 1	TU Wien 2
Matrix	Sediment, sludge	Leachate, concentrate, liquid waste	Drinking water, Ground water, WWTP effluent, process water	Sediment, soil, sludge	Drinking water, ground water	Surface water, wastewater	Drinking water, ground water, WWTP in- & effluent, process water	Sediment, soil, sludge, lettuce	Aqueous matrices	Sludge, sediment
Separation	UPLC	UPLC	UPLC	UPLC	UPLC	UPLC	UPLC	UPLC	HPLC	HPLC
Analyser	Triple quadrupole	Triple quadrupole	Triple quadrupole	Triple quadrupole	Triple quadrupole	Orbitrap (HRMS)	Orbitrap (HRMS)	Orbitrap (HRMS)	Triple quadrupole	Triple quadrupole
Sample preparation	Ultrasonic extraction w/ MeOH Sediment: concentrate	Dilution w/ H ₂ O+MeOH Washing water, permeate: DI	(DI)	(DI)	1:1 MeOH dilution Optional auto-SPE	Online-SPE	SLE	SPE	Solid: Online-SPE (Aqueous: DI)	Sludge: Ultrasonic extraction
# PFAS analytes	30	30	56	56	30	27	29	29	34	34
# extracted internal standards	1					19	20	20	24	24
# non-extracted internal calibration standards	19	19	22	22	19		2	2	7	7
LoQ in ng/L		15 - 75 (washing water, leachate) 1000 - 10000 (liquid waste)	15 - 100 (process water, WWTP effluent) 2 - 15 (groundwater, surface water)		1 - 5 (0.01 - 0.05 w/ automated SPE)	25 - 100	0.13 - 5.44 (surface water) 0.15 - 12.40 (effluent water) 0.69 - 49.60 (influent water)		1 - 10	
LoQ in µg/kg	10 - 50 (sludge) 0.050 - 0.250 (sediment)			0.040 - 0.300 (soil) 160 - 1200 (sludge)				0.13 - 4.96 (sediment) 0.04 - 9.92 (lettuce)		0.1 - 0.5 (soil) 1 - 20 (sludge)

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Table 2: List of abbreviations, acronyms and dimensions.

AFFF	Aqueous Film Forming Foam
AOF	Absorbable Organic Fluorine
CE	Collision Energy
CS	Case Study
DI	Direct injection
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EIS	Extracted Internal Standard
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ESI	Electrospray Ionisation
EU	European Union
(EU) DWD	Drinking Water Directive of the European Union
(EU) EQSD	Environmental Quality Standards Directive of the European Union
HDPE	High Density Polyethylen
HRMS	High Resolution Mass Spectrometry
IS	Internal Standard
LC	Liquid Chromatography
LoD	Limit of Detection
LoQ	Limit of Quantification
LVI	Large Volume Injection
M	mol/L
MDL	Method Detection Limit
MeOH	Methanol
MNS	Mixed Native Solution
MRM	Multiple Reaction Monitoring
MS	Mass Spectrometer
MS/MS	Tripple Quatrupol Mass Spectrometer
NF	Nanofiltration
NIS	Non-extracted Internal Standard
NTA	Non-Target Analysis
PE	Polyethylen
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluorinated Alkyl Substances
POCIS	Polar Organic Chemical Integrative Sampler
PP	Polypropylen
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
RO	Reversed Osmosis
RPM	Rounds Per Minute
RT	Retention Time
S/N	Signal to Noize Ratio
SLE	Solid-liquid extraction
SNS	Single Native Solution
SPE	Solid Phase Extraction
TF	Total Fluorine
TOP	Total Oxidizable Precursor Assay
TQ	Tripple Quatupol
UPLC	Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography
V	Volt
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

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1. Introduction – diverse methods for diverse analytical demands

1.1. Background

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are ubiquitous in the natural and human environment, thus contaminating all kinds of materials like waters, sludge, soils, sediments, air, biota, food, consumer products, among others (Buck et al., 2011; Evich et al., 2022; Glüge et al., 2020). Therefore, detecting PFAS contaminations requires analytical methods for various matrices and accordingly many different preparatory steps, depending on the contaminated object/matrix under consideration. In addition, with largely more than 10,000 different compounds (Buck et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2021), and vast variations with respect to concentrations (pg/L - mg/L, depending on the contamination), it is not possible to have one single analytical method feasible for all kinds of different

- matrices and/or
- PFAS compounds and/or
- ranges of concentrations and/or
- economic needs.

Therefore, analysers must focus particularly strongly on reflecting their specific needs prior to establishing any methodical details.

This document provides an overview on available methods for targeted PFAS analysis, as developed in the PROMISCES project (work package 1), for

- a set of typical and emerging PFAS contaminants
- in aqueous, solid, mixed/complex matrices
- at typical concentration ranges within the respective matrix
- with several complementary and concurrent approaches which allow reaching the same analytical goal with different techniques – helpful for differently instrumented laboratories.

The term “complex matrices” relates to solid and/or highly cross-contaminated matrices, containing substantial amounts of other contaminants and/or high amounts of harmless (yet analytically problematic) matrix constituents like dissolvable or solid organics, salts, or particulate matter.

Considering targeted PFAS, there is some compounds already included in some directives, such as the 20 from the EU Drinking Water Directive (including the ‘4 EFSA PFAS’), or candidate to the revision of the Water Framework Directive (24 compounds), but the objectives of the PROMISCES project is to potentially identify new compounds of interest, which implies to enlarge the list of measured compounds, in relation to the needs of case studies.

1.2. Analytical demands by case studies and work packages

According to the different analytical needs of every individual case, the case studies (CS) within the PROMISCES project defined the following analytical demands that needed to be addressed. The diversity of the below-shown demands consequently led to the development of several complementary methods, cf. Table 1 and Table 57.

- CS 1 (Berlin)
 - Aqueous matrix variability: Drinking/ground water, surface water & wastewater
 - PFAS substance range: Include at least the 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive (including the ‘4 EFSA PFAS’), as well as emerging PFAS of potential interest to the Berlin semi-closed urban water cycle (Gen-X, FOSA, ...)

- Low LoQs, as minimally required in the EU DWD, or lower; with a prospective achievement of the LoQs potentially required as laid out in the draft of the EU EQS Directive proposed by the SCHEER (2022)
- CS 2
 - Aqueous matrix variability: Drinking/ground water, surface water & wastewater
 - PFAS substance range: Include at least the 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive (including the '4 EFSA PFAS'), as well as emerging PFAS (Gen-X, FOSA, FTS, ...)
 - Low LoQs, as minimally required in the EU DWD, or lower; with a prospective achievement of the LoQs potentially required as laid out in the draft of the EU EQS Directive
- CS 3
 - Matrices variability: surface water, wastewater effluent & industrial wastewater, lettuce
 - PFAS substance range: Include at least the 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive (including the '4 EFSA PFAS'), as well as emerging PFAS of potential interest for industrial use (Gen-X, FOSA, ...)
- CS 4
 - Ability to analyse PFASs in complex matrices: landfill leachate, RO/NF concentrate and sewage sludge
 - Analysis suitable for high organic load
 - PFAS substance range: broad range at least the 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive (including the '4 EFSA PFAS'), as well as emerging PFAS (Gen-X, FOSA, ...) for a total of 30 analytes.
 - LOQs low enough to quantify the PFASs sought and close mass balances
- CS 5
 - Ability to analyse PFASs in complex matrices (sediments).
 - PFAS substance range: broad range at least the 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive (including the '4 EFSA PFAS'), as well as emerging PFAS (Gen-X, FOSA, ...) for a total of 30 analytes.
 - Possibility of going down to low LOQs by concentrating the extract as the sediment was found to be low in PFAS load.
- CS 6 and WP2 experiments
 - Solid matrices: soils, raw samples of AFFF and process water from remediation assays (with adjuvant, DMSO, Ethanol, PEG, Xanthane...), groundwater.
 - PFAS substance range: 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive, PFAS occurring in AFFF, degradation by-products; global OF characterization: TF/AOF, TOP assay.
- CS 7
 - Matrices: water (modified with chemical reagents) from WP3 batch and column experiments, groundwater and soils.
 - PFAS substance range: Include at least the 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive (including the '4 EFSA PFAS'), as well as emerging PFAS of potential interest for industrial use (Gen-X, FOSA, ...), and transformation products.
- WP3 experiments
 - Complex matrices: sludge, WWTP effluents, fertilizers.

- PFAS substance range: 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive, largest range of PFAS as possible: precursors, degradation by-products, 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive; global OF characterization: TF/ AOF, TOP assay.
- Task 1.4
 - Treated urban and industrial waste waters; POCIS extracts.
 - PFAS substance range: 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive, largest range as possible: precursors, degradation by-products, 20 PFAS of the EU Drinking Water Directive.

2. PFAS analysis in waters

This chapter lists analytical methods for aqueous matrices. The described methods are organized by their most relevant properties regarding the main analytical goals, i.e., if low limits of quantification are to be achieved, or if the method shall be very robust and easy to apply.

2.1. Low & ultra-low limits of quantification in ground & drinking water (BWB_1)

2.1.1. Goals

The first premise was optimization of a direct injection LC-MS/MS method for the below-listed set of PFAS-analytes (cf. Table 3) towards robustness and reproducibility for ground and drinking water samples. Secondly, optimization of the method aimed at limits of quantification in the single-digit ng/L-range. The method complies with German standard DIN 38407-F42 2011-03.

Following the preceding two optimization steps, extraction/substance enrichment prior to LC-MS/MS aimed at sub-ng/L-ranges for the limits of quantification for as many of the included substances as possible the approach uses solid phase extraction (SPE) of PFAS from drinking and ground waters with enrichment factors of at least 10 prior to direct injection (and quantification) of the extract into LC-MS/MS.

Table 3: List of PFAS targets and respective analytical details of the BWB_1 method.

#	Compound acronym	Retention time in min	ESI +/-	Precursor m/z	Fragment 1 m/z	Fragment 1 CE in V	Fragment 2 m/z	Fragment 2 CE in V	Internal Standard (IS) acronym	Precursor m/z	IS quantifier fragment	IS quantifier fragment CE in V
1	PFBA	3.47	-	213	169	8	-	-	M4PFBA	217	172...	5
2	PFBS	4.00	-	299	99	33	80	34	M3PFBS	302	80	37
3	PFPeA	4.00	-	263	219	6	69	41	M5PFPeA	268	223	5
4	PFPeS	4.60	-	349	99	36	80	40	M3PFHxS	402	80	49
5	PFHxA	4.54	-	313	269	6	119	24	M5PFHxA	318	273	5
6	PFHxS	5.30	-	399	99	44	80	42	M3PFHxS	402	80	49
7	PFHpA	5.20	-	363	319	6	169	15	M4PFHpA	367	322	5
8	PFHpS	5.98	-	449	99	46	80	50	M8PFOS	507	80	55
9	PFOA	6.00	-	413	369	7	169	15	M8PFOA	421	376	5
10	PFOS	6.90	-	499	99	45	80	50	M8PFOS	507	80	55
11	PFNA	6.88	-	463	419	8	219	16	M9PFNA	472	427	5
12	PFNS	7.73	-	549	99	48	80	76	M8PFOS	507	80	55
13	PFDA	4.74	-	513	469	10	169	20	M6PFDA	519	474	5
14	PFDS	8.55	-	599	99	54	80	60	M8PFOS	507	80	55
15	PFUnDA	8.60	-	563	519	10	169	24	MFPUnDA	570	525	5
16	PFUnDS	9.28	-	649	99	58	80	62	-	-	-	-
17	PFDoDA	9.57	-	613	569	12	169	30	MPPDoDA	615	570	9
18	PFDoDS	9.99	-	699	169	54	99	60	-	-	-	-
19	PFTTrDA	10.05	-	663	619	12	169	30	MPPDoDA	615	570	9
20	PFTTrDS	10.56	-	749	99	62	80	66	-	-	-	-
21	HFPO-DA (GEN X)	4.72	-	285	185	20	169	12	MHFPO-DA	287	169	12
22	FOSA	9.10	-	498	169	40	78	40	M8FOSA	506	78	60
23	4:2 FTS	4.56	-	327	307	21	81	29	M2-4:2FTS	329	309	21
24	6:2 FTS (H4-PFOS)	5.95	-	427	407	22	81	32	M2-6:2FTS	429	409	25
25	9Cl-PF3ONS	7.56	-	531	507	5	351	29	-	-	-	-
26	DONA	5.41	-	377	251	9	85	29	-	-	-	-
27	8:2 FTS	7.93	-	527	507	29	81	53	M2-8:2FTS	529	509	29
28	N-MeFOSAA	3.53	-	570	419	21	-	-	d3-N-MeFOSAA	573	419	21
29	N-EtFOSAA	8.20	-	584	575	5	499	29	d5-N-EtFOSAA	589	419	21
30	7HPFHpA	4.22	-	345	281	6	131	28	-	-	-	-

2.1.2. Material & Equipment

When choosing materials, it is crucial to avoid any components made of fluorinated materials. Especially fittings, tubing and septa are often made from or are coated with PTFE. There are several LC manufacturers who provide special kits to modify pump tubing and fittings in a running chromatography system. Also, it is important to bypass any kind of degasser. Membranes that are used in eluent degassing devices tend to leak PFAS blind values. A huge impact on background noise and blind value issues is coming from the eluents. To control this influence, it is recommended to use a delay column, which is installed downstream of the eluent pump in the solvent flow before the injector. This column delays peaks from possible blind values coming from contaminated chemicals. In the following tables the instruments (Table 4), materials (Table 5), and chemicals as well as reference standards (Table 6) are listed.

Table 4: List of Instruments for the BWB_1 method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC-MS/MS System	Agilent	TQ 6495C (Agilent PFAS-free Kit)
Analytical Column	Agilent	Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 3,0 x 100 mm, 1,8 µm
Delay Column	Agilent	Infinity Lab PFC delay column 4,6 x 30 mm

Table 5: List of materials for the BWB_1 method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Polypropylen Vials, 1.5 mL, screw cap	Th. Geyer GmbH & Co. KG	Short thread vial
Polypropylen Sample Flasks	VWR	Rinsed with MeOH
Pipettes	Eppendorf SE	10 µL- 1000 µL

Table 6: List of the chemicals and reference standards for the BWB_1 method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Methanol	Honeywell	Chromasolv LC-MS Ultra, tested for blind values
Ultrapure Water	Berrytec GmbH	Easy UP(UVUF) TOC with Merck KGaA EDS-Pak
Formic Acid	Biosolve	ULC-MS grade
Ammonium acetate	Sigma Aldrich	For mass spectrometry
Ammonium formate	Sigma Aldrich	For mass spectrometry
Reference Standard	Manufacturer	Description
PFAS-Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	PFAC30PAR 1 mg/L
Internal Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	MPFAC24ES 1 mg/L

2.1.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample should be collected with caution, to avoid any contamination from any material (e.g. Tubing Sealing, O-rings). The sample should be taken with a PP-scoop depending on the sampling location. The sample is filled up bubble-free into a 1000 mL PP plastic bottle and transported refrigerated. The sample is stored in the refrigerator at $< 8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until measurement (within 2 weeks) or deep frozen at $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In Lab Sample Preparation

To avoid adsorption effects of longer chained PFAS the samples are generally diluted 1:2 with methanol in the vial. In addition, an internal standard (IS) solution is added to each sample. The volumes for each sample are as follows: 50 μL IS + 450 μL methanol + 500 μL sample. If necessary, the samples are diluted in the vial with drinking water prior to measurement, e.g. 1:5, 1:10, 1:20 or 1:50. If higher dilutions are necessary, appropriate intermediate dilutions must be made.

Calibration standards

For an exact quantification an external calibration is used. Therefore, a minimum of five different concentrations are diluted with methanol from the standard stock-solution. The concentration range of the external calibration curve is from 0.0005 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 0.02 $\mu\text{g/L}$. In addition, 50 μL (equal to 10 ng/L) of the internal standard is also added to each calibration solution. To have a similar environment as in the samples the calibration solutions are prepared in the same way as the samples in a 1:2 dilution of water and methanol. For quality control a standard substance of the same compounds but from a different manufacturer is also diluted to a concentration of 10 ng/L in the same way as the calibration standard.

At the beginning and end of the sequence, the standard series and the control standard is measured. If there are more than 30 samples, the 0.005 $\mu\text{g/L}$ calibration point is measured again approximately in the middle of the sequence as a quality control. The signal of the blank sample before the first calibration point should be at maximum one third of the lower limit of quantification, otherwise the limit of quantification cannot be retained.

Extraction/Enrichment

To be able to analyse samples below the LOQ of the direct injection method an extraction of the samples can be performed. To enrich PFAS in samples of drinking, ground and surface water an aliquot of 100 mL is extracted via automated solid phase extraction (SPE). Depending on the dilution an enrichment factor of 10 - 100 is achieved. For the exact steps see Table 7.

A HDPE bottle is rinsed with methanol and dried thoroughly prior use. An aliquot of 200 mL of the water sample is filled in the sample bottle and spiked with 100 μL internal standard solution that is also used for quantification with the external calibration.

Table 7: Extraction steps for the automated solid phase extraction for the BWB_1 method.

Step	Details
1. Conditioning	1. 4 mL MeOH (+0.5 % NH ₃) 2. 4 mL MeOH 3. 4 mL Ultra-Pure Water
2. Loading	Loading Volume: 100 mL, pH 7 ± 0.5 Loading Speed: 10 mL/min
3. Washing	4 mL 25 mM Ammoniumacetate Buffer pH 4 (in Ultra-Pure-Water)
4. Drying	40 min under N ₂ -stream
5. Elution	Elution Volume: 10 mL MeOH (+0,1 % NH ₃) Elution Speed: 0.8 mL/min
6. Evaporation	Evaporate sample to 0.2 mL under vacuum 150 (mbara), reconstitute to 0.5 mL with MeOH

For technical reasons the smallest sample volume that can be handled through the automated SPE is 100 mL. After reconstitution of the eluate to 500 µL, 500 µL Ultra-Pure water is added to each sample eluate so the solution volume is 1 mL thus a factor of 100 is achieved.

2.1.4. Analysis

Instruments & Parameters

For measurements an Agilent 1290 Infinity II UHPLC coupled to an Agilent TQ 6495C triple quadrupole mass spectrometer is used. The ionisation is realised through an electrospray ionisation source (ESI) AJS. As analytical column an Agilent Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 (3.0 x 100 mm, 1.8 µm) is used at a temperature of 35 °C and an injection volume of 100 µL. Furthermore, an Agilent Infinity Lab PFC delay column (4.6 x 30mm) is installed. The separation is achieved by using a binary gradient mobile phase consisting of ultra-pure water with 2 mM Ammonium acetate buffer (A) and HPLC-MS grade methanol (B) at a constant flow of 0.5 mL/min. The mobile phase gradient starts at 95 % A and decreases to 40 % A within the first minute after injection. Following the gradient decreases eluent A to 5 % over 11 minutes. A clean-up of the analytical column is performed with 100 % B for 1 minute and is followed by a reconstitution step on start conditions at 95 % A for 3 minutes.

The mass spectrometers ESI source is operating in negative ion mode using multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) for the components as shown in Table 3. The capillary voltage was set to 3 kV. The sheath gas temperature is set at 400 °C and the drying gas temperature at 80°C, the flow was 12 L/min for the sheath gas and 13 L/min for the drying gas.

Quantification

The quantification of the measured samples is performed with Agilent Mass Hunter 10.5 software. The sample peaks are quantified via the relative response ratio obtained through the internal standard. The quantification of the individual features is due to the most abundant fragment (quantifier) and if possible, secured through another fragment (qualifier), the fragments are shown in Table 3. The linear calibration curve should have a correlation coefficient (R^2) of more than 0.99 for each compound and is weighted by $1/x$.

2.1.5. Performance

The limits of quantification (LOQ) listed in Table 8 are calculated as described in DIN 32645:2008-11.

Table 8: List of the limits of quantification (LOQ) of the BWB_1 method.

#	Compound acronym	LOQ in ng/L	#	Compound acronym	LOQ in ng/L
1	PFBA	1	16	PFUnDS	1.2
2	PFBS	0.4	17	PFDoDA	2
3	PFPeA	0.6	18	PFDoDS	0.8
4	PFPeS	0.8	19	PFTTrDA	2.2
5	PFHxA	0.6	20	PFTTrDS	1
6	PFHxS	0.4	21	HFPO-DA (GEN X)	2.6
7	PFHpA	0.8	22	FOSA	-
8	PFHpS	0.8	23	4:2 FTS	-
9	PFOA	0.4	24	6:2 FTS (H4-PFOS)	1
10	PFOS	0.6	25	9Cl-PF3ONS	-
11	PFNA	1.2	26	DONA	-
12	PFNS	0.4	27	8:2 FTS	-
13	PFDA	1.4	28	N-MeFOSAA	-
14	PFDS	1	29	N-EtFOSAA	-
15	PFUnDA	1.2	30	7HPFHpA	0.8

2.2. Low limits of quantification in surface & waste waters (BWB_2)

2.2.1. Goals

The goal of this method is to quantify PFAS-components in the nanogram per litre scale by online SPE-LC-MS. The targeted set of PFAS is shown in Table 9. To lower the impact of the waste- and surface water matrix online-SPE can be a cost-effective way to minimise the lab-time per sample while the LOQ is improved by injecting larger volumes.

Table 9: Details on the PFAS-Targets from BWB_2 method; ESI—electrospray ionisation, min—minutes, m/z—mass-to-charge, IS—internal standard

#	Compound acronym	Molecular Formula	Retention time in min	ESI +/-	Exact Mass m/z	Internal Standard (IS) acronym	Molecular Formula	Internal Standard (IS) exact mass m/z
1	PFBS	C4HF9O3S	5.81	-	298.94299	M3PFBS	¹³ C4HF9O3S	301.95306
2	PFPeS	C5HF11O3S	6.49	-	348.9398	M3PFHxS	¹³ C3C3HF13O3S	401.94667
3	PFHxA	C6HF11O2	6.43	-	312.97281	M5PFHxA	¹³ C5CHF11O2	317.98959
4	PFHxS	C6HF13O3S	4.77	-	398.9366	M3PFHxS		401.94667
5	PFHpA	C7HF13O2	6.81	-	362.96962	M4PFHpA	¹³ C4C3HF13O2	366.98304
6	PFHpS	C7HF15O3S	7.20	-	448.93341	M3PFHxS		401.94667
7	PFOA	C8HF15O2	7.25	-	412.96643	M8PFOA	¹³ C8HF15O2	420.99326
8	PFOS	C8HF17O3S	7.51	-	498.93022	M8PFOS	¹³ C8HF17O3S	506.95706
9	PFNA	C9HF17O2	7.55	-	462.96323	M9PFNA	¹³ C9HF17O2	471.99343
10	PFNS	C9HF19O3S	7.80	-	548.92702	M8PFOS		506.95706
11	PFDA	C10HF19O2	7.87	-	512.96004	M6PFDA	¹³ C6C4HF19O2	518.98017
12	PFDS	C10HF21O3	8.06	-	598.92383	-	-	-
13	PFUnDA	C11HF21O2	8.20	-	562.95684	M7PFUnDA	¹³ C7C4HF21O2	569.98033
14	PFDoA	C12HF23O2	8.37	-	612.95365	MPFDoA	¹³ C2C10HF23O2	614.96036
15	PFTrDA	C13HF27O3S	8.64	-	662.95046	-	-	-
16	HFPO-DA (GEN X)	C6HF11O3	6.56	-	284.9779	-	-	-
17	FBSA	C4H2F9NO2S	6.25	-	297.95898	-	-	-
18	FHxSA	C6H2F13NO2S	7.15	-	397.95259	-	-	-
19	FOSA	C8H2F17NO2S	7.76	-	497.9462	M8FOSA	¹³ C8H2F17NO2S	505.97304
20	4:2 FTS	C6H5F9O3S	6.11	-	326.97429	M2-4:2FTS	¹³ C2C4H5F9O3S	328.98100
21	6:2 FTS (H4-PFOS)	C8H5F13O3S	7.15	-	426.9679	M2-6:2FTS	¹³ C2C6H5F13O3S	428.97461
22	8:2 FTS	C10H5F17O3S	7.82	-	526.96152	M2-8:2FTS	¹³ C2C8H5F17O3S	528.96823
23	9Cl-PF3ONS	C8HClF16O4S	7.69	-	530.89558	-	-	-
24	11Cl-PF3OUdS	C10ClF20O4S	8.21	-	630.88919	-	-	-
25	N-MeFOSAA	C11H6F17NO4S	8.04	-	569.96733	d3-N-MeFOSAA	C11D3H3F17NO4S	572.98616
26	N-EtFOSAA	C12H8F17NO4S	8.16	-	583.98298	d5-N-EtFOSAA	C12D5H3F17NO4S	589.01436
27	NaDONA	C7H2F12O4	6.90	-	376.96887	-	-	-

2.2.2. Material & Equipment

When choosing materials, it is crucial to avoid any components made of fluorinated materials. Especially fittings, tubing and septa are often made from or are coated with PTFE. In the following tables the instruments (Table 10), materials (Table 11), and chemicals as well as reference standards (Table 12) are listed.

Table 10: List of Instruments for the BWB_2 method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC system	Thermo Fisher Scientific®	Dionex Mate 3000
MS system	Thermo Fisher Scientific®	Exactive Plus - Orbitrap HRMS
Analytical Column	Waters®	ACUITY UPLC HSS T3 1.8µm 2.1x50mm
SPE Column	Thermo Fisher Scientific®	Hypersil GOLD aQ 20x2.1

Table 11: List of material for the BWB_2 method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Polypropylen Vials, 1.5 mL, screw cap	Th. Geyer GmbH & Co. KG	Short thread vial
Polypropylen Sample Flasks	VWR	Rinsed with MeOH
Pipettes	Eppendorf SE	10 µL- 1000 µL
Pipette tips	Eppendorf SE	Various sizes

Table 12: List of the chemicals and reference standards for the BWB_2 method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Methanol	Honeywell	Chromasolv LC-MS Ultra, tested for blind values
Ultra-Pure Water	Berrytec GmbH	Easy UP(UVUF) TOC with Merck KGaA EDS-Pak
Formic Acid	Biosolve	ULC-MS grade
Ammonium acetate	Sigma Aldrich	For mass spectrometry
Ammonium formate	Sigma Aldrich	For mass spectrometry
Standard Drinking Water		PFAS blind value free
Calibration Solution	Thermo Scientific	Pierce LTQ Velos ESI Pos/Neg Ion
Reference Standard	Manufacturer	Description
PFAS-Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	e.g. PFAC30PAR 1 mg/L
Internal Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	e.g. MPFAC24ES 1 mg/L

2.2.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample should be collected with caution, to avoid any contamination from any material (especially Tubing Sealing, O-rings). The sample should be taken with a PP-scoop depending on the sampling location. The sample is filled bubble-free into a 50 mL PP plastic bottle and transported refrigerated. The sample is stored in the refrigerator at 5 °C until measurement (within 2 weeks) or deep freezed at -25 °C.

In Lab Sample Preparation

An aliquot of the sample is filled in a 1.5-mL-PE-vial and diluted with ultrapure-water on a ratio of 1:5 to 1:50 depending on the matrix. To each sample 20 µL of Internal standard solution (equals 0.1 µg/L) is added. The final volume should be 1500 µL.

Calibration Standards

For an exact quantification an external calibration is used. Therefore at least five different concentrations are diluted with ultrapure water from the standard solution. Additionally, 20 µL of the internal standard is added to each sample.

The concentration range of the external calibration curve is from 0.005 µg/L to 1 µg/L. In addition, 20 µL (equal to 100 ng/L) of the internal standard is also added to each calibration solution. Each vial should contain a volume of 1500 µL. For quality control a standard substance of the same compounds but from a different manufacturer is also diluted to a concentration of 100 ng/L in the same way as the calibration standard.

At the beginning of the sequence, the standard series and the control standard is measured. If there are more than 30 samples, the 0.04 µg/L calibration point is prepared and measured again approximately in the middle of the sequence as a quality control. The signal of the blank sample before the first calibration point should be at maximum one third of the lower limit of quantification, otherwise the limit of quantification cannot be retained.

2.2.4. Analysis

Instruments & Parameters

Thermo Fisher Scientific Dionex Labmate 3000 UHPLC system coupled to an Thermo Fisher Scientific Exactive Plus Orbitrap high resolution mass spectrometer is used. The ionisation is realised through an electrospray ionisation source (ESI). The Labmate 3000 system is equipped with a second pair of eluent pumps which is used as column cleaning eluents. A second Labmate 3000 pump system is used for the online SPE column. As analytical column an ACUITY UPLC HSS T3 (2.1x50 mm, 1.8 µm) is used at a temperature of 40 °C. As online SPE column a Thermo Fisher Hypersil GOLD aQ (20x2.1 mm) is used with an injection volume of 1000 µL. The separation is achieved by using a binary gradient mobile phase consisting of ultra-pure water with 1 % (v/v) methanol and 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid (A) and HPLC-MS grade methanol with 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid (B) at a constant flow of 0.6 mL/min. The mobile phase gradient starts at 1 % B and increases over 7 minutes to 95 % B at a static flow of 0.6 mL/min. A clean-up of the analytical column is performed with 99 % B for 2.5 minutes and is followed by a reconstitution step on start conditions at 99 % A for 3 minutes. AS detector a Thermo Fisher Scientific Exactive Plus is used the spectrometers ionisation source (ESI) is operating in negative ion mode. A mass calibration with Thermo Fisher Calibration Solution is performed each day prior to measuring. The capillary spray voltage is set to 3.6 kV. The sheath gas flow is set to 40 and the aux gas flow to 20 at 300 °C.

Quantification

The quantification of the measured samples is performed with Thermo Fisher Scientific Tracefinder 4.1 software. The sample peaks are quantified via the relative response ratio obtained through the internal standard. The linear calibration curve should have a correlation coefficient (R^2) of more than 0.99 for each compound and is weighted by $1/x$.

2.2.5. Performance

The limits of quantification (LOQ) listed in Table 13 are calculated as described in DIN 32645:2008-11.

Table 13: List of the limits of quantification (LOQ) of the BWB_2 method.

#	Abbreviation	LOQ in ng/L	#	Abbreviation	LOQ in ng/L
1	PFBS	35	15	PFTTrDA	75
2	PFPeS	42	16	HFPO-DA (GEN X)	50
3	PFHxA	34	17	FBSA	26
4	PFHxS	34	18	FHxSA	67
5	PFHpA	39	19	FOSA	80
6	PFHpS	42	20	4:2 FTS	50
7	PFOA	24	21	6:2 FTS (H4-PFOS)	24
8	PFOS	24	22	8:2 FTS	31
9	PFNA	24	23	9Cl-PF3ONS	40
10	PFNS	45	24	11Cl-PF3OUdS	50
11	PFDA	20	25	N-MeFOSAA	36
12	PFDS	37	26	N-EtFOSAA	41
13	PFUnDA	31	27	DONA	41
14	PFDoA	67			

2.3. Broad PFAS substance spectrum (BRGM_IPGP_1)

2.3.1. Goals

The goal of this method is to reach levels of quantification of PFAS-components at nanogram per litre scale by LC-MS/MS analysis. Direct injection and triple quadrupole liquid chromatography allow to reach this objective at ng/L concentration without SPE enrichment.

This method is also planned for monitoring of PFAS selected for experimentations (WP2 and WP3). Analysis will be focused on different compounds depending on the assays. Concentrations are mostly high ($\mu\text{g/L}$ or mg/L) but in very complex aqueous matrices (containing salts, oxidants, Xanthane etc.) that make very strong dilution (50 to 500) and large linearity range necessary.

Table 14: List of compounds and MS transitions for broad PFAS range method (BRGM_IPGP_1).

#	Acronym	ESI +/-	Retention time	Precursor m/z	Fragment 1 m/z	F1 CE in V	Fragment 2 m/z	F2 CE in V	Internal standard	Precursor m/z	Fragment 1 m/z	F1 CE in V	Fragment 2 m/z	F2 CE in V
1	PFBA	-	4.18	213	169	8			PFBA 13C4	217	172	8		
2	PFPeA	-	7.69	263	219	8	69	35	PFHxA 13C2	315	270	9	119	19
3	PFHxA	-	10.95	313	269	6	119	19	PFHxA 13C2	315	270	9	119	19
4	PFHpA	-	13.32	363	319	9	169	15	PFHxA 13C2	315	270	9	119	19
5	HPFHpA	-	10.03	345	281	10	131	23	PFHxA 13C2	315	270	9	119	19
6	PFOA	-	15.09	413	369	9	169	17	PFOA 13C4	417	372	11	169	17
7	PFNA	-	16.51	463	419	10	219	16	PFOA 13C4	417	372	11	169	17
8	PFDA	-	17.7	513	469	10	219	16	PFDA 13C2	515	470	10	219	16
9	P37DMOA	-	17.7	513	469	10	269	17	PFHxA 13C2	315	270	9	119	19
		-	17.7	469	269	20	219	22	PFHxA 13C2	315	270	9	120	19
10	PFUnDA	-	18.72	563	519	11	269	18	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
11	PFDoDA	-	19.59	613	569	12	169	24	PFUnDA 13C2	565	520	11	269	17
12	PFTTrDA	-	20.35	663	619	12	169	26	PFUnDA 13C2	565	520	11	269	17
13	PFTeDA	-	21.01	713	669	13	169	28	8:2 FTSA 13C2	529	509	25	81	32
14	PFHxDA	-	22.07	813	769	15	169	30	PFHxDA 13C2	815	770	15	169	30
15	PFODA	-	22.9	913	869	15	169	35	PFHxDA 13C2	815	770	15	169	30
16	PFPrS	-	5.42	249	80	23	119	20	PFBS 13C3	302	80	29	99	27
17	PFBS	-	8.73	299	80	27	99	26	PFBS 13C3	302	80	29	99	27
18	PFPeS	-	11.53	349	80	28	99	29	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
19	PFHxS	-	13.61	399	80	33	99	30	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
20	PFHpS	-	15.24	449	80	35	99	35	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
21	PFOS	-	16.58	499	80	37	99	37	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
22	PFECHS	-	14.98	461	381	24	99	25	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
23	PFNS	-	17.74	549	80	43	99	43	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
24	PFDS	-	18.73	599	80	43	99	43	PFUnDA 13C2	565	520	11	269	17
25	PFUnDS	-	19.58	649	80	45	99	45	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
26	PFDoDS	-	20.32	699	80	49	99	47	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
27	PFTTrDS	-	20.96	749	80	49	99	47	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
28	6:2 FTCA	-	13.83	377	293	16	313	7	8:2 FTSA 13C2	529	509	25	81	32
29	8:2 FTCA	-	16.94	477	393	15	413	7	PFDA 13C2	515	470	10	219	16
30	3:3 FTCA	-	7.57	241	177	7	137	13	8:2 FTUCA 13C2	459	394	15	244	30
31	5:3 FTCA	-	13.55	341	237	13	217	24	8:2 FTUCA 13C2	459	394	15	244	30
32	7:3 FTCA	-	16.81	441	337	12	317	22	8:2 FTUCA 13C2	459	394	15	244	30
33	8:3 FTCA (4H-PFUnDA)	-	18.03	491	387	12	367	20	8:2 FTUCA 13C2	459	394	15	244	30
34	8:2 FTUCA	-	16.85	457	393	15			8:2 FTUCA 13C2	459	394	15	244	30
35	4:2 FTSA	-	10.73	327	307	18	81	25	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
36	6:2 FTSA	-	15.0	427	407	22	81	30	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
37	8:2 FTSA	-	17.69	527	507	25	81	32	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
38	10:2 FTSA	-	19.63	627	607	28	81	40	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
39	6:2 diPAP	-	20.85	789	443	18	97	30	PFDoDA 13C2	615	570	12	319	18
40	8:2 diPAP	-	22.55	989	543	22	97	35	8:2 diPAP 13C4	993	545	22	97	35
41	DONA	-	13.53	377	251	10	85	25	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
42	6:2 Cl-PFESA	-	17.23	531	351	24	83	24	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
43	8:2 Cl-PFESA	-	19.16	631	451	27	83	28	PFOS 13C4	503	80	38	99	38
44	FBSA	-	11.64	298	78	20	119	17	PFBS 13C3	302	80	29	99	27
45	FHxSA	-	16.08	398	78	25	169	25	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
46	MeFBSA	-	15.22	312	219	16	112	18	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
47	FOSA	-	18.79	498	78	28	169	28	8:2 FTSA 13C2	529	509	25	81	32
48	MeFOSA	-	20.48	512	169	26	219	23	MeFOSA D3	515	169	26	219	24
49	EtFOSA	-	21.03	526	169	26	219	24	MeFOSA D3	515	169	26	219	24
50	MeFBSAA	-	11.98	370	283	12	312	16	PFBS 13C3	302	80	29	99	27
51	FOSAA	-	17.62	556	498	26	419	24	MeFOSAA D3	573	419	19	515	19
52	MeFOSAA	-	18.2	570	419	19	483	14	MeFOSAA D3	573	419	19	515	19
53	EtFOSAA	-	18.7	584	419	19	526	19	MeFOSAA D3	573	419	19	515	19
54	HFPO-DA	-	11.64	285	169	8	185	18	HFPO-DA 13C3	287	169	8	185	18
55	PFHxSAm	+	16.41	485	85	30	70	35	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	103	30
		-	16.41	483	169	27	319	22	PFHxS 18O2	403	84	33	104	30
56	6:2 FTAB	+		571	440	30	104	29						
		-		569	223	16	446	17						

2.3.2. Material & Equipment

When choosing materials, it is crucial to avoid any fluor-based components. For samples, Polystyrene tubes have been selected and tested to avoid sorption during storage.

Table 15: List of Instruments for the BRGM_IPGP method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC system	Waters®	ACQUITY H-CLASS
MS system	Waters®	XEVO-TQXS
Analytical Column	Waters®	ACQUITY UPLCBEH C18 1.7µm 2.1x100mm

Table 16: List of material for the BRGM_IPGP method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Injection vials	Waters	Polypropylen ,0.7 mL, screw cap

Table 17: List of chemicals for the BRGM_IPGP method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Methanol	BIOSOLVE CHIMIE	Abs. ULC-MS
Ultra-Pure Water	BIOSOLVE CHIMIE	Abs. ULC-MS
Ammonium acetate	Fischer Scientific	

Standards

Standards for PFAS were purchased from Wellington, Neochema, Cambridge Isotope Laboratory (CIL), Ehrenstorfer GmbH, Chiron and HPC standards. For radiolabelled compounds, standards were purchased from Wellington (both mix and individual compounds). Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample from experiment are collected in 10 mL PP tubes, stored in the refrigerator at 5°C until measurement (within 2 weeks) or keep freezed at -20 °C.

2.3.3. Sample Handling & Standards

In Lab Sample Preparation

The sample is diluted with water on a ratio of 1:10 to 1:1000 depending on the matrix and spiked concentrations. An aliquot of the sample is filled in a 0.7-mL-PP-vial. 20 µL of internal standards solution is added. The final volume should be 500 µL with a 50/50; methanol / water ratio.

Calibration Standards

Internal calibration is used, using at least nine different concentrations from 10 to 5000 ng/L for experimental samples and from 2 to 500 ng/L for other samples (not yet applied).

2.3.4. Analysis

Chromatography

At the beginning and end of the sequence, after control blank of the system, the standard series and the control standard are measured. Each 20 samples, control standards will be measured (20 % and

80 % of the linearity range. For the direct injection method for each sample a volume of 30 µL is injected.

For measurements an ACQUITY I-CLASS system coupled to an XEVO-TQXS triple quadrupole mass system is used. An electrospray ionisation source (ESI) is used. For the separation a binary gradient of MeOH 2mM ammonium acetate buffer (B) and ultra-pure water with a 2 mM ammonium acetate buffer is chosen. The gradient is described in Table 18.

Table 18: Binary gradient for the BRGM_IPGP method.

Time	Flow mL/min	% A	% B
0	0,3	95	5
1,0	0,3	75	25
23,0	0,3	0	100
27,0	0,3	0	100
27,1	0,3	95	5
30	0,3	95	5

Mass spectrometry

The mass spectrometers ESI was operating in both negative and positive ion modes using multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) for the components as shown in Table 14. The capillary voltage was set to 0.5 kV. The desolvation gas temperature was set to 550 °C and 1200 L/h for the desolvation flow, 150 L/h for the cone flow. Collision gas flow was set to 0.15 mL/min.

2.3.5. Performance

Methods has not been assessment on multiple real samples and need a complete validation (on going) for all compounds. Some adjustment in the announced LOQ can occurs.

Table 19: Performances of analytical method for the BRGM_IPGP

Compounds	Internal standard	LOQ (ng/L)	Compounds	Internal standard	LOQ (ng/L)
PFBA	M PFBA	2	8:2 FTUCA	M FTUCA	2
PFPrS	M PFBS	2	8:2 FTCA	M 8:2 FTSA	15
3:3 FTCA	M FTUCA	15	P37DMOA	M PFHxA	2
PFPeA	M PFHxA	2	6:2 Cl-PFESA	M PFOS	2
PFBS	M PFBS	2	FOSAA	M MeFOSAA	2
HPFHpA	M PFHxA	2	8:2 FTSA	M PFOS	2
4:2 FTSA	M PFHxS	2	PFDA	M PFDA	2
PFHxA	M PFHxA	2	PFNS	M PFOS	2
FBSA	M PFBS	2	4H-PFUnDA	M FTUCA	2
PFPeS	M PFHxS	2	MeFOSAA	M MeFOSAA	2
HFPO-DA	M HFPO-DA	5	FOSA	M 8:2 FTSA	2
MeFBSAA	M PFBS	2	EtFOSAA	M MeFOSAA	2
PFHpA	M PFHxA	2	PFDS	M PFUnDA	2
NaDONA	M FTUCA	2	PFUnDA	M PFOS	2
5:3 FTCA	M PFOS	2	8:2 Cl-PFESA	M PFOS	2
PFHxS	M PFHxS	2	PFUnDS	M PFOS	2
6:2 FTCA	M 8:2 FTSA	2	PFDoDA	M PFUnDA	2

MeFBSA	M PFHxS	2	10:2 FTSA	M PFOS	2
PFECHS	M PFOS	2	MeFOSA	M MeFOSA	2
6:2 FTSA	M PFHxS	15	PFDoDS	M PFOS	2
PFOA	M PFOA	5	PFTriDA	M PFUnDA	2
PFHpS	M PFHxS	2	EtFOSA	M MeFOSA	2
PFHxSA	M PFHxS	2	6:2 diPAP	M PFDODA	2
PFHxSAm	M PFHxS	2	PFTriDS	M 8:2 FTUCA	2
PFNA	M PFOA	2	PFTeDA	M 8:2 FTSA	2
PFOS	M PFOS	2	PFHxDA	M 8:2 FTSA	2
7:3 FTCA	M FTUCA	2	8:2 diPAP	M 8:2 diPAP	2
			PFODA	M 8:2 diPAP	15

2.4. Ultra-low limits of quantification in waters (CSIC_1)

2.4.1. Goals

This methodology allows the quantification of PFASs at low ng/L in different water types including drinking water, surface (clean), and water from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) namely influent and effluent waters.

The PFAS object of analyses are enriched and samples purified through SPE to a final volume of 100 µl, followed by their analysis by LC-HRMS.

The volumes depend on water type being 500 ml for clean waters, 200 ml of effluent waters and 50 ml for influent waters. Material & Equipment

As partners described in the above paragraphs, fluor-based components need to be substituted when possible and, when not, be sure that no cross-contamination is influencing in an overestimation of some PFAS in your samples. Being this, in CSIC we always carry out an extraction blank in parallel with the extraction of each set of samples to rule out or to monitor any possible cross contamination. On the other hand, all the fluor-materials from the lab procedures are eliminated in CSIC as well as all the devices from the UPLC system substituted for metal tubing.

Table 20: List of compounds and MS transitions for broad PFAS range method (CSIC_1).

#	Compound acronym	Retention time in min	ESI +/-	Precursor m/z	Fragment 1 m/z	Fragment 1 CE in V	Internal Standard (IS) acronym	Precursor m/z & quantifier	IS quantifier fragment CE in V
1	PFBA	0.54	-	212.9792	169	30	MPFBA	214.0612	30
2	PFPeA	0.83	-	262.9760	219	30	M5PFPeA	268.386	30
3	PFHxA	1.5	-	312.9728	269	30	M5PFHxA	318.3828	30
4	PFHpA	3.48	-	362.9696	319	30	M4PFHpA	367.2976	30
5	PFOA	5.15	-	412.9664	369	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
6	PFNA	5.94	-	462.9632	419	30	M9PFNA	472.7012	30
7	PFDA	6.70	-	512.9600	469	30	M6PFDA	519.45203	30
8	PFUnA	7.3	-	562.9568	519	30	M7PFUnDA	570.5308	30
9	PFDoA	7.76	-	612.9536	569	30	MPFDoA	614.0356	30
10	PFTTrDA	8	-	662.9504	619	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
11	PFTeDA	8.5	-	712.9472	669	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
12	PFHxDA	10.8	-	812.9408	769	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
13	PFODA	12.0	-	912.9344	869	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
14	PFBS	0.9	-	298.9429	80	30	M3PFBS	302.1889	30
15	PFPeS	2.8	-	348.9397	80	30	M3PFBS	302.1889	30
16	PFHxS	3.92	-	398.9366	80	30	M3PFHxS	402.1826	30
17	PFHpS	4.5	-	448.9334	80	30	M3PFHxS	402.1826	30
18	PFOS	6.12	-	498.9302	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
19	PFNS	6.8	-	548.9270	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
20	PFDS	7.1	-	598.9238	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
21	PFDoS	8.2	-	698.9174	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
22	FOSA	7.35	-	497.9462	78	30	M8FOSA	506.6022	30
23	4:2 FTSA	1.81	-	326.9742	307	30	M2-4:2FTS	329.1382	30
24	6:2 FTSA	5.21	-	426.9679	407	30	M2-6:2FTS	429.1319	30
25	8:2 FTSA	6.77	-	526.9615	507	30	M2-8:2FTS	529.1255	30
26	10:2 FTSA	8.2	-	626.9551	607	30	M2-8:2FTS	529.1255	30
27	6:2 diPAP	5.6	-	788.9750	97	30	M4-6:2diPAP	793.3030	30
28	8:2 diPAP	6.1	-	988.96227	543	30	M4-8:2diPAP	993.29027	30
29	ADONA	3.22	-	376.9688	251	30	M4PFHpA	367.2976	30
30	EtFOSA	6.7	-	525.9775	169	30	M8FOSA	506.6022	30
31	EtFOSAA	6.85	-	583.9829	419	30	d-N-EtFOSAA	584.9903	30
32	FOSAA	6.5	-	555.95168	419	30	d-N-MeFOSAA	570.9747	30
33	MeFOSAA	6.72	-	569.9673	419	30	d-N-MeFOSAA	570.9747	30
34	MeFOSA	6.2	-	511.9618	169	30	M8FOSA	506.6022	30
35	HFPO-DA (Gen-X)	0.8	-	328.96772	285	30	MGenX	330.0497	30
36	PFMOAA	0.6	-	178.9773	-	-	MGenX	330.0497	30
37	PFMOPrA	0.7	-	228.9741	-	-	MGenX	330.0497	30
38	PFMOBA	1.1	-	278.9709	-	-	MGenX	330.0497	30
39	PFO2HxA	2.1	-	244.9690	85	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
40	PFO3OA	3.4	-	310.9607	85	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
41	PFO4DA	5.1	-	376.9524	85	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
42	9CI-PF3ONS	4.8	-	530.8955	351	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
43	11CI-PF3OUdS	6.9	-	630.8891	451	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30

2.4.2. Material & Equipment

Table 21: List of instruments for the CSIC method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC system	Waters	Acquity LC (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) system
Analytical Column	Thermo Fischer	Hypersil GOLD PFP 50 x 3 mm (3 µm)

Table 22: List of material for the CSIC method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Glass Vials, 1.5 mL, pre-slit silicone cap	LABBOX labware s.	Short thread vial
250 µl glass insert vials	Agilent	n.a
Polypropylen Sample Flasks	Falcon	Sterilized
Micropipet	Eppendorf SE	10 µL- 5000 µL
Syringes	Hamilton	1 µL- 500 µL
Pasteur pipetes	Serviquimia	Not necessary

Table 23: List of chemicals and reference standards for the CSIC method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Methanol	Chromasolv	Chromasolv LC-MS Ultra, tested for blind values
Water	Chromasolv	Chromasolv LC-MS Ultra, tested for blind values
Ammonium hydroxide	Merck	25 %
Ammonium acetate	Sigma Aldrich	For mass spectrometry
Standard References	Manufacturer	Description
PFAS-Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	1 - 5 mg/L
Internal Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	2 mg/L

2.4.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

Samples are collected in PP or HDPE bottles clean bottles and transported to the analytical laboratory under cool conditions. Once there, the samples are preserved at -20 °C until analysis.

In Lab Sample Preparation

Samples are defrosted and spiked with 10 µl of extraction internal standards mixture (to have a final concentration of 20 ng/ml in vial). Then, samples are vigorously shaken and left to reach the equilibrium for 30 min before to proceed with SPE extraction.

Calibration standards

The quantification is based on external calibration curve normalized with extraction internal standards. In this sense, the calibration curve is performed with three dilutions to minimize operator errors and to have an adequate number of calibration points (min of 5 points) between 0.1 and 150

ng/ml (in vial), in 100 µl of methanol:water (1:9). Finally, the curve is spiked with 10 µl of surrogate internal standard mixture, agitated and preserved at -20 °C until its use.

Extraction/Enrichment

The purification and extraction consist of SPE with Oasis WAX 6 cc or 3 cc, depending on the turbidity of the samples (influent vs effluent). The enrichment factor is of 5000 for clean waters, 2000 for effluent waters and 500 for influent waters. Next Table 24 summarizes the main steps during the SPE procedure.

Table 24: Main SPE steps for the CSIC method.

Step	Details
1. Conditioning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 4 mL MeOH (0.1 % NH₄OH) 2. 4 mL MeOH 3. 4 mL Ultra-Pure Water
2. Loading	Loading Volume under vacuum conditions Loading Speed: 1 mL/min
3. Washing	Not necessary
4. Drying	15 min under vacuum conditions
5. Elution	Elution Volume: 10 mL MeOH (0.1 % NH ₄ OH) Elution Speed: under gravity conditions
6. Evaporation	Evaporate sample near to dryness under N ₂ stream and transfer to a LC vial equipped with an insert and dry again the rest of the solvent
7. Reconstitution	Reconstitution in 100 µl of methanol:water (1:9)

2.4.4. Analysis

Analysis of PFASs

The chromatographic separation of the compounds is carried out using liquid chromatography equipped with a Hypersil GOLD PFP column (50 x 3; from Thermo Scientific™) under gradient conditions with methanol (20 mM NH₄Ac) and water (20 mM NH₄Ac) with a 10 µL injection volume. The chromatographic system is coupled to an HRMS QExactive-Orbitrap analyser equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in negative. Data acquisition is by exact mass in full scan mode at a resolution power of 70,000 measured at full width at half maximum (FWHM) and, in parallel, in data dependent scan of the most intense ions, acquired at a resolution of 17,500 (FWHM) that provides the MS² confirmation. The data processing is through Xcalibur 3.0 software. The parameters considered for the identification of the PFASs are the exact mass, the fragmentation pattern in MS² when necessary and the retention time compared to the patterns of the pure standard compounds.

Quantification of PFASs

The quantification is carried out by calibration curve normalized by corresponding internal standard signal. All the calibration curves have more than 0.9 R² with a deviation of the calibration points within -25 % and 25 %.

2.4.5. Performance

The experimental calculation of MLOD and MLOQ, recoveries and precision for the different compounds is carried out according to (Llorca et al. 2012), Table 25.

Table 25: MLOQ of the CISC_1 method for surface, effluent and influent waters.

	Surface water (ng/L)	Effluent water (ng/L)	Influent water (ng/L)
PFBA	0.14	3.52	14.07
PFPeA	0.14	0.15	1.55
PFHxA	0.15	0.38	1.53
PFHpA	0.16	0.40	1.61
PFOA	0.15	0.55	0.69
PFNA	0.13	0.31	1.26
PFDA	0.99	3.47	13.88
PFUnA	1.21	3.01	10.43
PFDoA	1.68	4.20	11.03
PFTTrDA	1.68	4.20	11.03
PFTeDA	5.44	8.10	10.44
PFHxDA	2.08	5.20	20.80
PFODA	4.96	12.40	49.60
PFBS	0.31	0.76	3.06
PFPeS	0.30	0.76	3.04
PFHxS	0.31	0.77	3.09
PFHpS	0.40	0.99	3.98
PFOS	0.37	0.91	3.66
PFNS	0.49	2.24	8.95
PFDS	0.46	1.50	6.00
PFDoS	2.30	5.00	10.93
FOSA	0.60	1.00	3.91
4:2 FTSA	0.50	1.00	4.00
6:2 FTSA	0.50	1.00	4.00
8:2 FTSA	0.50	1.00	4.00
10:2 FTSA	1.00	2.00	7.00
6:2 diPAP	0.20	0.50	2.00
8:2 diPAP	1.00	2.50	10.00
ADONA	0.50	1.25	5.00
EtFOSA	0.20	0.50	2.00
EtFOSAA	0.20	0.50	2.00
FOSAA	0.20	0.50	2.00
MeFOSAA	0.20	0.50	2.00
MeFOSA	0.20	0.50	2.00
HFPO-DA (Gen-X)	0.50	1.25	5.00
PFMOAA	0.20	0.50	2.00
PFMOPrA	1.00	2.50	10.00
PFMOBA	1.00	2.50	10.00
PFO2HxA	0.20	0.50	2.00
PFO3OA	0.20	0.50	2.00
PFO4DA	1.00	2.50	10.00

2.5. Broad matrix spectrum (TU Wien_1)

For the balancing of different systems (e.g. river, WWTP, etc.) is necessary to determine of PFASs concentration in samples with various matrices. The focus of this work was to develop the methods for the determination of PFASs in the low concentration range in liquid samples.

2.5.1. Goal

The following methodology described the possibility quantitative analysis of PFASs in different matrix. The samples with water matrix (surface water, wastewater, landfill leachate) should be prepare with solid phase extraction (SPE) and analysed by LC-MS.

Table 26: List of PFAS targets, internal standards, and respective analytical details of the TU Wien methods.

#	Compound acronym	Retention time in min	ESI +/-	Precursor m/z	Fragment 1 m/z	Fragment 1 CE in V	Fragment 2 m/z	Fragment 2 CE in V	Extracted Internal Standard (EIS) acronym	EIS quantifier fragment m/z	EIS quantifier fragment CE in V	Non-extracted internal standard (NIS) acronym	NIS quantifier fragment m/z	NIS quantifier fragment CE in V
1	PFBA	4.1	-	213	169	-13	147	-10	MPFBA_13C4	172	-13	M3PFBA-13C3	172	-12
2	PFPeA	4.7	-	263	219	-11	197	-10	M5PFPeA_13C5	223	-11	MPFHxA_13C2	270	-14
3	PFHxA	5.2	-	313	269	-14	119	-28	M5PFHxA_13C5	273	-14			
4	PFHpA	5.8	-	363	319	-14	169	-24	M4PFHpA_13C4	322	-14			
5	PFOA	6.4	-	413	369	-13	219	-20	M8PFOA_13C8	172	-25	MPFOA_13C4	372	-13
6	PFNA	7.1	-	463	419	-14	218	-22	M9PFNA_13C9	427	-4	MPFNA_13C5	423	-14
7	PFDA	7.8	-	513	469	-16	269	-26	M6PFDA_13C6	474	-16	MPFDA_13C2	470	-16
8	PFUdA	8.4	-	563	519	-18	269	-24	M7PFUdA_13C7	525	-18			
9	PFDoA	8.9	-	613	569	-18	319	-22	MPFDoA_13C2	570	-18			
10	PFTrDA	9.4	-	663	619	-20	169	-38	M2PFTeDA_13C2	670	-22			
11	PFTeDA	9.8	-	713	669	-22	169	-42						
12	PFBS	4.8	-	299	80	-36	99	-80	M3PFBS_13C3	99	-36	MPFHxS_1802	103	-66
13	PFPeS	5.2	-	349	99	-80	119	-40	M3PFHxS_13C3	80	-66			
14	PFHxS	5.8	-	399	80	-66	99	-66						
15	PFHpS	6.4	-	449	80	-66	99	-66	M8PFOS_13C8	80	-120	MPFOS_13C4	80	-120
16	PFOS	7.1	-	499	80	-120	99	-100						
17	PFNS	7.7	-	549	80	-100	99	-100						
18	PFDS	8.3	-	599	80	-112	99	-64						
19	4:2 FTS	5.1	-	327	307	-28	81	-38	M2-4:2 FTS_13C2	309	-28	MPFOS_13C4	80	-120
20	6:2 FTS	6.4	-	427	407	-32	81	-64	M2-6:2 FTS_13C2	409	-32			
21	8:2 FTS	7.7	-	527	507	-64	81	-76	M2-8:2 FTS_13C2	509	-40			
22	PFOSA	8.3	-	498	78	-85	64	-128	M8FOSA_13C8	78	-85	MPFHxA_13C2	270	-14
23	N-MeFOSA	8.2	-	512	169	-37	-	-	d-N-MeFOSA_d3	169	-37			
24	N-EtFOSA	8.5	-	526	219	-36	169	-37	d-N-EtFOSA_d5	169	-37			
25	N-MeFOSAA	5.4	-	570	419	-36	-	-	d3-N-MeFOSAA	419	-39			
26	N-EtFOSAA	5.9	-	584	419	-36	526	-28	d5-N-EtFOSAA	419	-36			
27	HFPO-DA	7.4	-	285	169	-10	-	-	M3HPFO-DA_13C3	169	-10	MPFHxA_13C2	270	-14
28	NaADONA	8.6	-	377	251	-15	85	-39	MPFDoA_13C2	570	-18/	MPFOA_13C4	172	-26
29	9Cl-PF3ONS	10.4	-	531	351	-36	-	-	M3PFHxS_13C3	80	-66	MPFOS_13C4	80	-120
30	¹¹ Cl-PF3OUdS	10.8	-	631	451	-40	199	-36	M3PFHxS_13C3					
31	PFHxDA	9.4	-	813	769	-24	-	-	M4PFHpA_13C4	322	-14	MPFDA_13C2	470	-16
32	PFODA	9.8	-	913	869	-26	-	-	M6PFDA_13C6	474	-16			
33	N-MeFOSE	9.4	-	616	59	-12	-	-	d7-N-MeFOSE	59	-12	MPFOS_13C4	80	-120
34	N-EtFOSE	9.7	-	630	59	-12	-	-	d9-N-EtFOSE	59	-12			

2.5.2. Material & equipment

Table 27: List of instruments for the TU Wien method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC system	PAL	PAL RTC
	Agilent	Agilent 1260 Infinity II
MS/MS system	sciex	Qtrap 6500+
Analytical Column	phenomenex	Phenomenex Luna Omega 3 μm PS C18 ; 150x5 , 100 Å
Delay Column	phenomenex	phenomenex Luna C18 50x3 mm 110 Å

Table 28: List of material for the TU Wien method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Polypropylen Vials, 1.5 mL, screw cap	Macherey&Nagel	Short thread vial
Polypropylen Sample Flasks	Azlon	Rinsed with Ethanol and DW
Pipettes	Finn	10 μL - 5000 μL

Table 29: List of chemicals for the TU Wien method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Methanol	Merck	CAS 67-56-1 (Merck, 20864.290)
Ultra Pure Water	Elga Veolia,	MiliQ Purelab Chorus 2+
Ammoniumhydroxyde	Merck	CAS 1335-21-6; (Merck1.05432.1000)

Table 30: List of reference standards for the TU Wien method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
PFAS-Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	PFAC30PAR 1 mg/L, MXI 1mg/L,
Internal Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	MPFAC-HIF-IS 1 mg/L, MPFAC-HIF-ES 1 mg/L

2.5.3. Sample Preparation & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample should be collected without any contamination from any material (e.g. Tubing Sealing, O-rings). The sample can be taken with a PP-scoop depending on the sampling location. The sample is filled bubble-free into a 1000 mL HDPE plastic bottle, transported refrigerated and stored in the refrigerator at 5°C until measurement.

Calibration Standards

For direct injection an external calibration was used for quantification. Therefore at least five different concentrations are diluted with methanol from the standard solution. The concentrations range from 50 ng/L to 1000 ng/L in the vial. In addition, 50 μL of the non-extracted internal standards (NIS) and extracted internal standards (EIS) is also added to each calibration solution. EIS was for

establish of recovery and NIS to establish of initial calibration used. For the exact assignment of internal standards to native substances see Table 46.

SPE Extraction/Enrichment

For extraction and enrichment of liquid analyse samples under the LOQ of the direct injection method a solid phase extraction (SPE) of the samples should be performed. To enrich PFAS in samples of ground and surface water an aliquot of 250 mL and for wastewater (influent, effluent) 100 ml is extracted via manual SPE. Depending on the dilution an enrichment factor of 10 - 100 is achieved. For the exact steps see Table 31. All reusable items (HDPE bottle, tubes, syringe etc.) is rinsed with ethanol and ultra-pure-Water prior to use. An Aliquot of the water sample is filled in the sample bottle and spiked with 50 µL of the internal standard solution (EIS) that is also used to dilute the calibration standard for quantification. As a positive control sample, reference compound PFAS in ultra-pure water (1 ng/L) is used.

Table 31: Condition of SPE Extraction for the TU Wien method.

Step	Details
1. Conditioning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2 mL MeOH 2 mL Ultra-Pure Water
2. Loading	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Loading Volume: 250 mL, (groundwater, surface water, effluent) 100 mL, (influent WWTP, Landfill Leachate) Loading Speed: 10 mL/min
3. Washing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 mL 25 mM Ammonium acetate in Ultra-Pure-Water
4. Drying	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Put cartridges in falcon tubes and centrifuge at 4000 rpm for 6 min.
5. Elution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2x1 mL MeOH (+1 % NH₄OH), each into appropriate glass vessel using pressurized air Elution Speed: 0.8 mL/min
6. Transfer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 mL of the eluate into a HPLC vial

After application of SPE 2 mL of the eluate with MeOH (+1 % NH₄OH) is collected. 1 mL of eluate was transferred to polypropylene vials (1.5 mL) and spiked with 50 µL of the internal standard solution (NIS).

2.5.4. Analysis

Chromatography direct injection

For PFASs determination with LCMS and direct injection a calibration curve is by injection of pure standard and the control standard generated. Always after 12 samples, a calibration standard series was made for control of stability of system. The blank sample before all calibration series should be injected for determination of limit of quantification measured.

For injection a PAL RTC sampler, for separation an Agilent 1290 Infinity II HPLC pump and for measurement a Sciex Qtrap 6500+ with electrospray ionisation source (ESI) by -3000 V and 350°C temperature was used.

As analytical column a Phenomenex Luna Omega 3 µm PS C18 100 x 3.0 mm 100 Å was used at a temperature of 40 °C and an injection volume of 40 µL. Furthermore, a delay column Phenomenex Luna C18; 50 x 3 mm 110 Å was installed.

The separation is achieved by using a binary gradient mobile phase consisting of ultra-pure water with 20 mM Ammonium acetate buffer (A) and HPLC-MS grade methanol (B) at a constant flow of 0.6 mL/min. The conditions of gradient show the Table 52.

Table 32: Conditions for the binary gradient for the TU Wien method.

Time	Mobile phase A	Mobile phase B	Flow
min	%		mL/min
0.00	90	10	0.600
1.50	35	65	0.600
8.00	5	95	0.600
8.10	1	99	0.600
12.00	1	99	0.600
12.10	90	10	0.600
16.00	90	10	0.600

Chromatography large volume injection (LVI)

For determination of higher ng/L concentration levels of PFASs in aqueous samples with “weak matrix” it's possible to use large volume injection (LVI). The great advantage in this case that we don't have to use SPE. Equal conditions as for direct injection were for LVI used, only the sample preparation before injection (diluted with mobile phase A:B, 90:10 %) and increasing of injection volumes (until 1000 µL) has been changed.

Mass spectrometry

The mass spectrometers ESI was operating in negative ion mode using multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) for the components as shown in the Table 46 and voltage was set to -3000 V. The sheath gas temperature was 350 °C and the drying gas temperature 80°C.

Analysis

The analysis of the measurements is performed with Sciex Analyst 1.7 and OS software. Due to the internal standard the standard and sample measurements is normalized. The peak detection parameters are as follows.

The volumes depend on water type being 250 ml for clean waters, 200 ml of effluent waters and 100 ml for influent waters. For sludge 1 g of sample was for ultrasonic extraction used. In all the cases, the method is robust and reproducible with good limits of quantification (MLOQ) for selected compounds (Table 53).

2.5.5. Performance

Table 33: MLOQ for the TU Wien Methods for water samples (surface water, effluent, influent)

Compound acronym	Surface water	Influent	Effluent
	LOQ [ng/L]		
PFBA	0.6	7.3	1.1
PFPeA	1.0	5.5	3.8
PFHxA	0.9	3.4	3.3
PFHpA	0.5	1.9	1.9
PFOA	1.0	0.7	0.7
PFNA	0.5	1.5	1.5
PFDA	0.8	0.3	0.3
PFUnDA	1.6	1.8	1.8
PFDoDA	0.7	1.3	1.3
PFTTrDA	0.5	1.0	1.0
PFTeDA	1.7	1.3	1.3
PFBS	0.3	2.1	1.9
PFPeS	0.6	1.3	0.6
PFHxS	0.2	1.1	1.1
PFHpS	0.3	0.6	0.6
PFOS	0.3	1.5	1.2
PFNS	0.2	0.4	0.4
PFDS	0.2	0.3	0.3
4:2 FTS	0.3	1.5	1.5
6:2 FTS	0.2	0.3	0.3
8:2 FTS	0.4	0.2	0.2
PFOSA	0.2	0.2	0.2
N-MeFOSAA	0.3	0.4	0.4
N-EtFOSAA	0.3	0.6	0.6
HFPO-DA2 GenX	0.2	0.2	0.2
NaADONA	0.1	0.4	0.4
9Cl-PF3ONS	0.2	1.0	1.0
11Cl-PF3OUdS	0.2	0.4	0.4
N-MeFOSA	0.3	1.4	1.4
N-EtFOSA	0.3	1.2	1.2
N-MeFOSE	0.2	1.2	1.2
N-EtFOSE	0.2	1.6	1.6

3. PFAS analysis in complex matrices

This chapter lists analytical methods for complex matrices as sludge, sediment, leachate, concentrate and permeate by NF/RO treatment. The described methods are organized by their most relevant properties regarding the main analytical goals, i.e. if the method shall be very robust and easy to apply.

3.1. Solid waste matrices: sludge and contaminated and treated sediment (ACEA_1)

3.1.1. Goals

The objective of this work was to identify and develop a cost-effective testing method for PFAS analysis in complex matrices such as sludge and sediment. The tested method was designed to be easily replicable and transferable to any testing laboratory operating in support of industrial operators.

Table 34: List of analytes for the ACEA_1 method.

Compound	Retention Time (min)	Precursor (m/z)	Fragment 1 (m/z)	Collision Energy (V)	Fragment 2 (m/z)	Collision Energy (V)	Internal Standard	Precursor (m/z)	Fragment 1 (m/z)	Collision Energy (V)
PFBA	2.45	213	169	9			MPFBA	217	172	9
PFPeA	2.71	263	219	9			M5PFPeA	268	223	8
4-2 FTS	2.83	327	81	26	287	23	M4-2 FTS	329	309	18
PFHxA	3.1	313	119	19	269	9	M5PFHxA	318	273	9
GENX	3.3	285	169	5	185	5				
PFBS	3.4	299	80	34	99	29	M3PFBS	302	80	29
C6O4	3.45	339	113	10	179	5				
PFHpA	3.64	363	169	16	319	9	M4PFHpA	367	322	9
6-2 FTS	3.85	427	81	30	407	21	M6-2 FTS	429	409	21
NaDONA	3.86	377	85	30	251	15				
PFPeS	4.02	349	99	34	80	31				
PFOA	4.32	413	219	15	369	9	PFOA-C13	421	172	20
PFHxS	4.77	399	99	39	80	35	M3PFHxS-1	402	80	40
PFNA	5.11	463	219	15	419	9	M9PFNA	472	427	9
8-2 FTS	5.34	527	81	35	507	24	M8-2 FTS-1	529	509	24
PFHpS	5.6	449	99	38	80	36				
N-MeFOSAA	5.9	570	419	18	512	20	d3-NmeFOSAA	573	419	20
PFDA	5.95	513	269	16	469	9	M6PFDA	519	474	9
N-EtFOSAA	6.42	584	419	18	526	18	d5-NetFOSAA	589	419	20
PFOS	6.46	499	99	47	80	40	PFOS-C13	507	80	40
PFUdA	6.83	563	269	17	519	9	M7PFUdA	570	525	9
PFNS	7.32	549	99	42	80	41				
FOSA	7.44	498	78	29	478	23	M8FOSA	506	78	35
PFDoA	7.7	613	319	18	569	9	PFDoA-C13	615	169	24
PFDS	8.16	599	99	44	80	43				
PFTTrDA	8.56	663	169	25	619	9				
PFUdS	8.96	649	99	45	80	45				
PFTeDA	9.39	713	319	20	669	9	PFTeDA-C13	715	169	24
PFDoS	9.71	699	99	50	80	50				
PFTTrDS	10.4	749	99	50	80	50				

3.1.2. Material & Equipment

When choosing materials, it is essential to avoid any fluor-based components. Fittings, tubing and septa are often made of or lined with PTFE. There are several LC manufacturers who can provide special kits to modify pumps tubing and fittings in an operating chromatography system. It is also important to exclude any type of degasser. Membranes used in eluent degassing devices tend to leak PFAS blind values Background noise and blind values have a significant impact on eluents. To control this influence, it is advisable to use a delay column, installed downstream of the eluent pump in the solvent stream before the injector. This device delays possible blind values resulting from contaminated chemicals. Extensive kinetics studies have been carried out to minimize the quantification error of long-chain analytes due to their instability and interference with the container walls.

Table 35: List of material for the ACEA_1 method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Glassworks	VWR	Class A calibrated flasks and cylinders for phase preparation
Injection vials	Phenomenex	Glass vials with crimper caps, for constituting and storing standard solutions and samples
Micropipet	Eppendorf SE	10 µL- 5000 µL
Scale	Mettler Toledo	Technical scales, with a size unit of at least 0.01 g
Filters	Whatman	Cellulose acetate filters, with 0.2µm porosity
Filters	Sartorius	RC filters 0.2 µm

Table 36: List of instruments for the ACEA_1 method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC system	Thermo Fisher Scientific	UHPLC UltiMate 3000 equipped with pumps, refrigerated autosampler, thermostated column compartment and degasser
MS system	Thermo Fisher Scientific	TSQ Altis triple quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with ESI source
Analytical Column	Phenomenex	Luna Omega 1.6µm PS C18 100Å, 100 x 2.1 mm

Table 37: List of chemicals for the ACEA_1 method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Acetonitrile	BIOSOLVE CHIMIE	Abs. ULC-MS
Ultra-pure water	BIOSOLVE CHIMIE	Abs. ULC-MS
Methanol	Fischer Scientific	Abs. ULC-MS
Ammonium acetate	VWR	LC-MS grade >99%

Reference materials:

Standard working mixtures are prepared from commercially available certified material purchased by CIL, Ultra Scientific and Wellington Lab.

3.1.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample should be collected carefully to avoid contamination by any material (e.g., pipe seals, O-rings). The sample should be taken with a metal-scoop depending on the sampling location. The sample is filled into a 1000 mL PP plastic or glass bottle and transported to a refrigerator. The sample is stored in the refrigerator at 5 °C until measured (within 2 weeks) or frozen at -25 °C. Sediment is dried at 105 °C before extraction.

In Lab Sample Preparation

Sediment contaminated e/o treated

1 g of solid matrix is weighted into a 15-50 mL polypropylene (or glass) centrifuge tube.

Extraction deuterated standard (M2PFUdA, 500 ng/kg for sediment and 100 µg/kg for sludge is added. After an equilibration time of 30 minutes, the extraction is done with 10mL of methanol. The sample is vortexed and sonicated for 30 minutes at room temperature.

After centrifugation (4000 rpm, 5 min), supernatant is transferred into glass or polypropylene conical-bottomed vials and dried ($T \leq 55$ °C) under flux of N_2

The sample is resolved with 1 mL of Methanol, transferred in centrifuge tube (4000 rpm, 5 min)

Supernatant is diluted 5 times (for sediment) and at least 100 times (for sludges), resulting in a 70:30 Water: Methanol mixture. The extract is injected after adding of the internal standard mixture.

Calibration standards

Samples are analysed using the same LC-MS/MS conditions as used to generate the Internal Calibration. Samples are warmed to room temperature and mix well prior to transferring to vials.

Internal calibration

Internal Calibration (ICAL) is performed continuously, at the head of each analytical session, on at least n. 5 levels starting from a minimum concentration of not less than 10 ng/L until 250 ng/L.

The operator can use a different criterion if he can demonstrate the effectiveness of the solution

If the concentration of any target analyte exceeds the ICAL range of the system, the prepared sample or sample extract should be diluted with 30:70 methanol-water containing and reanalysed. If dilutions cannot be performed, concentrations that exceed the calibration range must be qualified as estimated.

Extraction/Enrichment

The laboratory monitors the recoveries of isotopically labelled surrogate for each matrix. The percent recovery of each surrogate should fall within the acceptance criteria (70 %-130 %). If surrogate do not meet the acceptance criteria, reanalysis and/or preparation of samples may be warranted. Otherwise, the associated target analytes may be reported with appropriate data qualifiers.

3.1.4. Analysis

Acceptance criteria for calibration:

Correlation coefficient (r) should be ≥ 0.995 (or $R^2 \geq 0.99$)

Calculated error (deviation): ≤ 30 %, on the first or most representative transition (≤ 50 % near LLOQ)

Relative Standard Error: ≤ 20 %,

In case of a negative result, calibration is repeated after performing maintenance operations, which are designed to increase instrumental sensitivity (interface cleaning, pre-column or column

replacement, mobile phase replacement, etc.), optimizing the chromatography of the system, and if necessary, in the most complex cases, technical assistance can be called in.

Chromatography

At the beginning and end of the sequence, the standard series and the control standard are measured. If there are more than 30 samples, the 10 ng/L calibration point is measured approximately in the middle of the sequence as a control. The blank laboratory sample before the first calibration series should be a maximum of one third of the lower limit of quantification, otherwise the limit of quantification cannot be observed.

Instrumental conditions:

- Blank: 70 % Water/ 30 % Methanol
- Injection volume: 100 µL
- Column temperature: 40°C
- Autosampler Temperature: 25°C
- Run Time: 22 min

Analytical conditions:

The binary gradient consists of the aqueous eluent A (ultra-pure water + 5 mM ammonium acetate) and the eluent B (Acetonitrile). All analytical conditions are shown in Table 38.

Table 38: Analytical conditions of the ACEA_1 method.

Time	Flow mL/min	B%	ESI Negative Ion (V)	2500
0.0	0.3	2	Sheat gas (Arb)	50
0.5	0.3	2	Aux gas (Arb)	10
0.6	0.3	40	Sweep gas (Arb)	1
14.0	0.3	100	Ion Transfer Tube T °C	325
15.0	0.3	100	Vaporizer T °C	300
16.0	0.3	2		
22.0	0.3	2		

Mass spectrometry

The ESI mass spectrometers operated in negative ion mode using multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) for components. Product ions used for quantification must have a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) ≥ 10 and are listed in the table. For most target analytes, a secondary product ion is identified to support qualitative identification. All secondary product ions must have an S/N ≥ 3 (for PFBA, PFOSA, and PFPeA, secondary product ions with sufficient relative abundance may not be identified at low concentration). Measurement analysis is performed with UltiMate 3000 Thermo Scientific Chromelion software. Due to the internal standard, the standard and sample measurements are normalized. Peak detection parameters are defined to optimize chromatographic peak integration. The operator verifies that the integration is preferably valley/valley.

3.1.5. Performance

The limits of quantification (LOQ) for sediments and sludge are listed in table 30 and are calculated as described in EPA Method 8327:2021 and EPA 40 CFR Appendix B to Part 136, Methods has been assessment on multiple real samples and have been validate for all compounds. Some adjustment in the announced are occurred.

Table 39: Limits of Quantification for the ACEA_1 method.

#	Matrix Abbreviation	sediment LOQ in µg/Kg	sludge LOQ in µg/Kg
1	PFBA	0,11	10
2	PFPeA	0,05	10
3	4-2 FTS	0,05	10
4	PFHxA	0,05	10
5	PFBS	0,05	10
6	GENX	0,05	10
7	C6O4	0,25	50
8	PFHpA	0,05	10
9	PFPeS	0,05	10
10	NaDONA	0,05	10
11	6-2 FTS	0,05	10
12	PFOA	0,05	10
13	PFHxS	0,05	10
14	PFNA	0,05	10
15	8-2 FTS	0,05	10
16	PFHpS	0,05	10
17	PFDA	0,05	10
18	N-MeFOSAA	0,05	10
19	PFOS	0,05	10
20	N-EtFOSAA	0,05	10
21	PFUdA	0,05	10
22	PFNS	0,05	10
23	PFDoA	0,05	10
24	PFDS	0,05	10
25	FOSA	0,05	10
26	PFTTrDA	0,05	10
27	PFUdS	0,05	10
28	PFTeDA	0,05	10
29	PFDoS	0,05	10
30	PFTTrS	0,05	10

3.2. Solid waste matrices: sludge and contaminated and treated soil (BRGM_IPGP_2)

3.2.1. Goal

Objective of the method is to develop a method for PFAS precursors on sludge, soil and compost samples. After liquid/solid extraction, different solid phase purification steps have been evaluated, but due to the complexity and heterogeneity of the treated matrices, and of the behaviour of each chemical groups of PFAS, a common procedure cannot be identified. Considering the need of the project and the range of concentration targeted, a dilution of the sample extract has been retained. Equipment, material, list of compounds, and analytical methods are the same as in method BRGM_IPGP_1.

3.2.2. Material & Equipment

When choosing materials, it is crucial to avoid any fluor-based components. For samples, Polystyrene tubes have been selected and tested to avoid sorption during storage.

Table 40: List of Instruments for the BRGM_IPGP_2 method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC system	Waters®	ACQUITY H-CLASS
MS system	Waters®	XEVO-TQXS
Analytical Column	Waters®	ACQUITY UPLCBEH C18 1.7µm 2.1x100mm
Laboratory centrifuge		

Ultrasonic bath		
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Table 41: List of material for the BRGM_IPGP method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Injection vials	Waters	Polypropylen ,0.7 mL, screw cap
20 mL Tubes	Falcon	
Centrifuge tube.		15 mL polypropylen

Table 42: List of chemicals for the BRGM_IPGP method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Methanol	BIOSOLVE CHIMIE	Abs. ULC-MS
Ammonium hydroxide	Fischer Scientific	
Ammonium acetate	Fischer Scientific	

Standards

Standards for PFAS were purchased from Wellington, Neochema, Cambridge Isotope Laboratory (CIL), Ehrenstorfer GmbH, Chiron and HPC standards. For radiolabelled compounds, standards were purchased from Wellington (both mix and individual compounds).

Calibration Standards

Internal calibration is used, using at least nine different concentrations from 10 to 5000 ng/L for experimental samples and from 2 to 500 ng/L for other samples (not yet applied).

3.2.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample from experiment are collected in 10 mL PP tubes, stored in the refrigerator at 5 °C until measurement (within 2 weeks) or keep freezed at -20 °C. Sludges are sampled and stored freezed at -20°C.

Sample preparation include drying at 35°C during 24h and crushing at 2 mm. After that samples are stored in desiccator and fridge for 1 week or kept freezed at -20 °C

Sample preparation

1 g solid sample was extracted sequentially with: 2 x 4 mL methanol with 1 % ammonium hydroxide and 4 mL methanol with 100 mM ammonium acetate). Between each step sample are vortexed, and ultra-sonicated for 20 min, then centrifuged (500 rpm, 5 min) and extract recovered. The three extracts are pooled and evaporated until 2 mL (to suppress ammonium hydroxide and ammonium acetate) for storage. Before analysis, specific dilution occurs if needed (tenfold for sludge in methanol). 100 µL of extract were completed with 50 µL of internal standard, 50 µL of methanol and 200 µL of water adjusted with 0.6 % of acetic acid.

3.2.4. Analysis

Chromatography

At the beginning and end of the sequence, after control blank of the system, the standard series and the control standard are measured. Each 20 samples, control standards will be measured (20 % and 80 % of the linearity range. For the direct injection method for each sample a volume of 30 µL is injected.

For measurements an ACQUITY I-CLASS system coupled to an XEVO-TQXS triple quadrupole mass system is used. An electrospray ionisation source (ESI) is used. For the separation a binary gradient of MeOH 2mM ammonium acetate buffer (B) and ultra-pure water with a 2 mM ammonium acetate buffer is chosen. The gradient is described in Table 18.

Table 43: Binary gradient for the BRGM_IPGP method.

Time	Flow mL/min	% A	% B
0	0,3	95	5
1,0	0,3	75	25
23,0	0,3	0	100
27,0	0,3	0	100
27,1	0,3	95	5
30	0,3	95	5

Mass spectrometry

The mass spectrometers ESI was operating in both negative and positive ion modes using multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) for the components as shown in Table 14. The capillary voltage was set to 0.5 kV. The desolvation gas temperature was set to 550 °C and 1200 L/h for the desolvation flow, 150 L/h for the cone flow. Collision gas flow was set to 0.15 mL/min.

3.2.5. Performance

Due to the lack of realistic matrix without PFAS, estimation of LOQ has been done on real sample. Extracts are diluted and spiked with internal standards until suppression of matrix effects. By this approach only the compounds already occurring in the sample can be assess. Theoretical LOQ based on sample mass, extraction volume, and dilution factor can also be used. Both data are presented in Table 44.

Table 44: LOQ for the BRGM_IPGP_2 method, based on real sample (sludge) and theoretical ones (1 g per sample, dilution factor 40).

Name	LOQ based on real sample ng/g	Theoretical LOQ ng/g	Name	LOQ based on real sample ng/g	Theoretical LOQ ng/g
10:2 FTSA	0.21	0.16	PFBA	0.15	0.16
3:3 FTCA	0.24	1.2	PFBS	0.13	0.16
4:2 FTSA	-	0.16	PFDA	0.18	0.16
4H-PFUnDA	0.4	0.16	PFDoDA	-	0.16
5:3 FTCA	-	0.16	PFDoDS	0.16	0.16
6:2 Cl-PFESA	0.15	0.16	PFDS	0.16	0.16
6:2 diPAP	-	0.16	PFECHS	0.15	0.16
6:2 FTCA	-	0.16	PFHpA	0.13	0.16

6:2 FTSA	-	1.2
7:3 FTCA	-	0.16
8:2 Cl-PFESA	-	0.16
8:2 diPAP	0.14	0.16
8:2 FTCA	0.13	1.2
8:2 FTSA	-	0.16
8:2 FTUCA	0.13	0.16
EtFOSA	-	0.16
EtFOSAA	0.11	0.16
FBSA	-	0.16
FOSA	-	0.16
FOSAA	-	0.16
HFPO-DA	0.14	0.4
HPFHpA	0.15	0.16
MeFBSA	0.18	0.16
MeFBSAA	0.11	0.16
MeFOSA	0.12	0.16
MeFOSAA	0.17	0.16
NaDONA	0.14	0.16
P37DMOA	0.15	0.16

PFHpS	0.11	0.16
PFHxA	0.15	0.16
PFHxDA	0.15	0.16
PFHxS	0.17	0.16
PFHxSA	-	0.16
PFHxSAm	-	0.16
PFNA	0.15	0.16
PFNS	0.09	0.16
PFOA	0.16	0.16
PFODA	-	1.2
PFOS	0.2	0.16
PFPeA	0.2	0.16
PFPeS	0.16	0.16
PFPrS	0.17	0.16
PFTeDA	-	0.16
PFTrDS	0.19	0.16
PFTriDA	-	0.16
PFUnDA	0.15	0.16
PFUnDS	0.22	0.16

3.3. Landfill leachate and liquid waste by NF/RO treatment (ACEA_2)

3.3.1. Goals

The objective of this work was to identify and develop a cost-effective testing method for PFAS analysis in complex matrices as leachate and liquid waste. The test method was designed to be easily replicable and transferable to any testing laboratory operating in support of industrial operators. The developed procedure and the obtained performance ensure robustness, reliability and fast turnaround time, with low material costs, high throughput (more than 20 samples per day) and meet the needs for continuous PFAS control and monitoring in complex matrices.

For the list of analytes see Table 34 in section 3.1.

3.3.2. Material & Equipment

When choosing materials, it is essential to avoid any fluor-based components. Fittings, tubing and septa are often made of or lined with PTFE. There are several LC manufacturers who can provide special kits to modify pumps tubing and fittings in an operating chromatography system. It is also important to exclude any type of degasser. Membranes used in eluent degassing devices tend to leak PFAS blind values Background noise and blind values have a significant impact on eluents. To control this influence, it is advisable to use a delay column, installed downstream of the eluent pump in the solvent stream before the injector. This device delays possible blind values resulting from contaminated chemicals. Extensive kinetics studies have been carried out to minimize the quantification error of long-chain analytes due to their instability and interference with the container walls. For a list of the materials, instruments, chemicals see Table 35, Table 36 and Table 37 in section 3.1.

3.3.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample should be collected carefully to avoid contamination by any material (e.g., pipe seals, O-rings). The sample should be taken with a metal-scoop depending on the sampling location. The sample is filled into a 1000 mL PP plastic or glass bottle and transported to a refrigerator. The sample is stored in the refrigerator at 5°C until measured (within 2 weeks) or frozen at -25 °C.

In Lab Sample Preparation

Liquid waste (leachate, feed, concentrate):

The sample is 20-fold diluted with methanol in a Class A glass or PP flask, vortexed, transferred into a polypropylene (or glass) centrifuge tube of the appropriate volume and centrifuged (4000 rpm, 5 min). The centrifuged extract is diluted by 5 times to obtain a Water: Methanol mixture with at least 30 % methanol and the internal standard mixture is added.

Liquid waste (permeate and washing waste)

For permeate and washing water, direct injection of the aliquot taken after filtration on RC 0.2 µm is used.

Calibration standards

Samples are analysed using the same LC-MS/MS conditions as used to generate the Internal Calibration. Samples are warmed to room temperature and mix well prior to transferring to vials.

Internal Calibration

Internal Calibration (ICAL) is performed continuously, at the head of each analytical session, on n. 5 levels in the working range 10- 250 ng/l. If the concentration of any target analyte exceeds the ICAL range of the system, the prepared sample or sample extract should be diluted with 30:70 methanol-water containing and reanalysed. If dilutions cannot be performed, concentrations that exceed the calibration range must be qualified as estimated.

Extraction/Enrichment

Samples are prepared using an appropriate preparation method (e.g., solvent dilution or extraction) to determinate 30 analytes of the perfluoroalkyl family of substances from liquid or solid environmental matrices of interest optimized ad hoc according to LOQ and S/N requirements. For liquid waste such as leachate, feed and concentrate, it was decided to apply a dilution procedure. For permeate and wash waste, direct injection was applied.

3.3.4. Analysis

For analytical conditions see section 3.1.

3.3.5. Performance

The limits of quantification (LOQ) for leachate and liquid waste are listed in table 34 and are calculated as described in EPA Method 8327:2021 and EPA 40 CFR Appendix B to Part 136.

Methods has been assessment on multiple real samples and have been validate for all compounds. Some adjustment in the announced are occurred.

Table 45: Limits of Quantification for the ACEA_2 method.

Matrix	Leachate	Concentrate	Permeate and washing waste	Matrix	Leachate	Concentrate	Permeate and washing waste
Abbreviation	LOQ in ng/L	LOQ in ng/L	LOQ in ng/L	Abbreviation	LOQ in ng/L	LOQ in ng/L	LOQ in ng/L
PFBA	1000	10000	15	PFHpS	1000	1000	15
PFPeA	1000	5000	15	PFDA	1000	1000	15
4-2 FTS	1000	1000	15	N-MeFOSAA	1000	1000	15
PFHxA	1000	10000	15	PFOS	1000	1000	15
PFBS	1000	10000	15	N-EtFOSAA	1000	1000	15
GENX	1000	1000	15	PFUdA	1000	1000	15
C6O4	5000	5000	75	PFNS	1000	1000	15
PFHpA	1000	1000	15	PFDoA	1000	1000	15
PFPeS	1000	1000	15	PFDS	1000	1000	15
NaDONA	1000	1000	15	FOSA	1000	1000	15
6-2 FTS	1000	1000	15	PFTTrDA	1000	1000	15
PFOA	5000	5000	15	PFUdS	1000	1000	15
PFHxS	1000	1000	15	PFTTeDA	1000	1000	15
PFNA	1000	1000	15	PFDoS	1000	1000	15
8-2 FTS	1000	1000	15	PFTTrS	1000	1000	15

3.4. Broad matrix spectrum (TU Wien_2)

For the balancing of different systems (e.g. river, WWTP, etc.) is necessary to determine of PFASs concentration in samples with various matrices. The focus of this work was to develop the methods for the determination of PFASs in the low concentration range in solid samples.

3.4.1. Goal

The following methodology described the possibility quantitative analysis of PFASs in different matrix. For solid samples (sludge and sediment) an ultrasonic extraction with and without SPE should be used before LC-MS analysis.

Table 46: List of PFAS targets, internal standards, and respective analytical details of the TU Wien methods.

#	Compound acronym	Retention time in min	ESI +/-	Precursor m/z	Fragment 1 m/z	Fragment 1 CE in V	Fragment 2 m/z	Fragment 2 CE in V	Extracted Internal Standard (EIS) acronym	EIS quantifier fragment m/z	EIS quantifier fragment CE in V	Non-extracted internal standard (NIS) acronym	NIS quantifier fragment m/z	NIS quantifier fragment CE in V
1	PFBA	4.1	-	213	169	-13	147	-10	MPFBA_13C4	172	-13	M3PFBA-13C3	172	-12
2	PFPeA	4.7	-	263	219	-11	197	-10	M5PFPeA_13C5	223	-11	MPFHxA_13C2	270	-14
3	PFHxA	5.2	-	313	269	-14	119	-28	M5PFHxA_13C5	273	-14			
4	PFHpA	5.8	-	363	319	-14	169	-24	M4PFHpA_13C4	322	-14			
5	PFOA	6.4	-	413	369	-13	219	-20	M8PFOA_13C8	172	-25	MPFOA_13C4	372	-13
6	PFNA	7.1	-	463	419	-14	218	-22	M9PFNA_13C9	427	-4	MPFNA_13C5	423	-14
7	PFDA	7.8	-	513	469	-16	269	-26	M6PFDA_13C6	474	-16	MPFDA_13C2	470	-16
8	PFUdA	8.4	-	563	519	-18	269	-24	M7PFUdA_13C7	525	-18			
9	PFDoA	8.9	-	613	569	-18	319	-22	MPFDoA_13C2	570	-18			
10	PFTTrDA	9.4	-	663	619	-20	169	-38	M2PFTTeDA_13C2	670	-22			
11	PFTTeDA	9.8	-	713	669	-22	169	-42						
12	PFBS	4.8	-	299	80	-36	99	-80	M3PFBS_13C3	99	-36		103	-66

13	PFPeS	5.2	-	349	99	-80	119	-40										
14	PFHxS	5.8	-	399	80	-66	99	-66	M3PFHxS_13C3	80	-66	MPFHxS_18 O2						
15	PFHpS	6.4	-	449	80	-66	99	-66										
16	PFOS	7.1	-	499	80	-120	99	-100	M8PFOS_13C8	80	-120	MPFOS_13C 4	80					
17	PFNS	7.7	-	549	80	-100	99	-100										
18	PFDS	8.3	-	599	80	-112	99	-64										
19	4:2 FTS	5.1	-	327	307	-28	81	-38	M2-4:2 FTS_13C2	309	-28							
20	6:2 FTS	6.4	-	427	407	-32	81	-64	M2-6:2 FTS_13C2	409	-32							
21	8:2 FTS	7.7	-	527	507	-64	81	-76	M2-8:2 FTS_13C2	509	-40							
22	PFOSA	8.3	-	498	78	-85	64	-128	M8FOSA_13C8	78	-85							
23	N-MeFOSA	8.2	-	512	169	-37	-	-	d-N- MeFOSA_d3	169	-37							
24	N-EtFOSA	8.5	-	526	219	-36	169	-37	d-N-EtFOSA_d5	169	-37							
25	N- MeFOSAA	5.4	-	570	419	-36	-	-	d3-N-MeFOSAA	419	-39							
26	N-EtFOSAA	5.9	-	584	419	-36	526	-28	d5-N-EtFOSAA	419	-36							
27	HFPO-DA	7.4	-	285	169	-10	-	-	M3HPFO- DA_13C3	169	-10	MPFHxA_13 C2	270					-14
28	NaADONA	8.6	-	377	251	-15	85	-39	MPFDoA_13C2	570	-18/	MPFOA_13C 4	172					-26
29	⁹ Cl- PF3ONS	10.4	-	531	351	-36	-	-	M3PFHxS_13C3	80	-66	MPFOS_13C 4	80					
30	¹¹ Cl- PF3OUdS	10.8	-	631	451	-40	199	-36	M3PFHxS_13C3									
31	PFHxDA	9.4	-	813	769	-24	-	-	M4PFHpA_13C4	322	-14	MPFDA_13C 2	470					-16
32	PFODA	9.8	-	913	869	-26	-	-	M6PFDA_13C6	474	-16							
33	N-MeFOSE	9.4	-	616	59	-12	-	-	d7-N-MeFOSE	59	-12	MPFOS_13C 4	80					-120
34	N-EtFOSE	9.7	-	630	59	-12	-	-	d9-N-EtFOSE	59	-12							

3.4.2. Material & equipment

Table 47: List of instruments for the TU Wien method.

Instruments	Manufacturer	Description
LC system	PAL	PAL RTC
	Agilent	Agilent 1260 Infinity II
MS/MS system	sciex	Qtrap 6500+
Analytical Column	phenomenex	Phenomenex Luna Omega 3 µm PS C18 ; 150x5 , 100 Å
Delay Column	phenomenex	phenomenex Luna C18 50x3 mm 110 Å

Table 48: List of material for the TU Wien method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
Polypropylen Vials, 1.5 mL, screw cap	Macherey&Nagel	Short thread vial
Polypropylen Sample Flasks	Azlon	Rinsed with Ethanol and DW
Pipettes	Finn	10 µL- 5000 µL

Table 49: List of chemicals for the TU Wien method.

Chemical	Manufacturer	Description
Methanol	Merck	CAS 67-56-1 (Merck, 20864.290)
Ultra-Pure Water	Elga Veolia,	MiliQ Purelab Chorus 2+
Ammoniumhydroxyde	Merck	CAS 1335-21-6; (Merck1.05432.1000)

Table 50: List of reference standards for the TU Wien method.

Material	Manufacturer	Description
PFAS-Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	PFAC30PAR 1 mg/L, MXI 1mg/L,
Internal Standards (Mix and Single Substances)	Wellington Laboratories	MPFAC-HIF-IS 1 mg/L, MPFAC-HIF-ES 1 mg/L

3.4.3. Sample Preparation & Standards

Sample Collection, Preservation and Storage

The sample should be collected without any contamination from any material (e.g. Tubing Sealing, O-rings). The sample can be taken with a PP-scoop depending on the sampling location. The sample is filled bubble-free into a 1000 mL HDPE plastic bottle, transported refrigerated and stored in the refrigerator at 5°C until measurement.

Calibration Standards

For direct injection an external calibration was used for quantification. Therefore at least five different concentrations are diluted with methanol from the standard solution. The concentrations range from 50 ng/L to 1000 ng/L in the vial. In addition, 50 µL of the non-extracted internal standards (NIS) and extracted internal standards (EIS) is also added to each calibration solution. EIS was for establish of recovery and NIS to establish of initial calibration used. For the exact assignment of internal standards to native substances see Table 46.

Ultrasonic extraction for sludge

For extraction and enrichment of solid analyse samples under the LOQ of the direct injection method an ultrasonic extraction of the samples has been performed. For the exact steps see Table 51.

Table 51: Condition of ultrasonic extraction for the TU Wien method.

Step	Details
1. sample preparation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sedimentation 2. Drying lyophilisation 3. Dewatering centrifuge
2. sample preparation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1-2 g of sample 2. 50 µL EIS; vortex 3. 10 mL MetOH 4. vortex
3. Ultrasonic extraction (US)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1 h/ 40°C/30 min
4. Separation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. centrifuge 6 min/4000 rpm
5. Evaporation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. N2/ 50°C; to 0,5 mL

7. Reconstitute the eluates	1. to 1,5 mL with MetOH (+1 % NH ₄ OH)
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After US-extraction and evaporation, 1 mL of the reconstitute eluates was transferred to polypropylene vials (1.5 mL), spiked with 50 µL of the internal standard solution (NIS) and analysed with LC-MS.

3.4.4. Analysis

Chromatography direct injection

For PFASs determination with LCMS and direct injection a calibration curve is by injection of pure standard and the control standard generated. Always after 12 samples, a calibration standard series was made for control of stability of system. The blank sample before all calibration series should be injected for determination of limit of quantification measured.

For injection a PAL RTC sampler, for separation an Agilent 1290 Infinity II HPLC pump and for measurement a Sciex Qtrap 6500+ with electrospray ionisation source (ESI) by –3000 V and 350°C temperature was used.

As analytical column a Phenomenex Luna Omega 3 µm PS C18 100 x 3.0 mm 100 Å was used at a temperature of 40 °C and an injection volume of 40 µL. Furthermore, a delay column Phenomenex Luna C18; 50 x 3 mm 110 Å was installed.

The separation is achieved by using a binary gradient mobile phase consisting of ultra-pure water with 20 mM Ammonium acetate buffer (A) and HPLC-MS grade methanol (B) at a constant flow of 0.6 mL/min. The conditions of gradient show the Table 52.

Table 52: Conditions for the binary gradient for the TU Wien method.

Time	Mobile phase A	Mobile phase B	Flow
min	%		mL/min
0.00	90	10	0.600
1.50	35	65	0.600
8.00	5	95	0.600
8.10	1	99	0.600
12.00	1	99	0.600
12.10	90	10	0.600
16.00	90	10	0.600

Chromatography large volume injection (LVI)

For determination of higher ng/L concentration levels of PFASs in aqueous samples with “weak matrix” it's possible to use large volume injection (LVI). The great advantage in this case that we don't have to use SPE. Equal conditions as for direct injection were for LVI used, only the sample preparation before injection (diluted with mobile phase A:B, 90:10 %) and increasing of injection volumes (until 1000 µL) has been changed.

Mass spectrometry

The mass spectrometers ESI was operating in negative ion mode using multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) for the components as shown in the Table 46 and voltage was set to -3000 V. The sheath gas temperature was 350 °C and the drying gas temperature 80°C.

Analysis

The analysis of the measurements is performed with Sciex Analyst 1.7 and OS software. Due to the internal standard the standard and sample measurements is normalized. The peak detection parameters are as follows.

The volumes depend on water type being 250 ml for clean waters, 200 ml of effluent waters and 100 ml for influent waters. For sludge 1 g of sample was for ultrasonic extraction used. In all the cases, the method is robust and reproducible with good limits of quantification (MLOQ) for selected compounds (Table 53).

3.4.5. Performance

Table 53: MLOQ for the TU Wien Methods for water samples (surface water, effluent, influent) and solid sample

Compound acronym	Soil/Sludge LOQ [ng/kg]
PFBA	100-5000
PFPeA	100-5000
PFHxA	100-5000
PFHpA	100-5000
PFOA	100-5000
PFNA	100-5000
PFDA	100-5000
PUnDA	100-5000
PDoDA	100-5000
PTrDA	100-5000
PTeDA	100-5000
PFBS	100-5000
PFPeS	100-5000
PFHxS	100-5000
PFHpS	100-5000
PFOS	100-5000
PFNS	100-5000
PFDS	100-5000
4:2 FTS	100-5000
6:2 FTS	100-5000
8:2 FTS	100-5000
PFOSA	100-5000
N-MeFOSAA	100-5000
N-EtFOSAA	100-5000
HFPO-DA2 GenX	100-5000
NaADONA	100-5000
9Cl-PF3ONS	100-5000
11Cl-PF3OUdS	100-5000
N-MeFOSA	100-5000

N-EtFOSA	100-5000
N-MeFOSE	100-5000
N-EtFOSE	100-5000

3.5. PFAS in Sediments and Plants (CSIC_2)

3.5.1. Goals

The analysis of solid matrices, including sediments and plants, has been carried out in IDAEA-CSIC for more than 10 years. The method is based in cost-effective extraction that has been improved for the inclusion of each new PFAS. This method covers the analysis PFAS from solid matrices. Despite the laboratory handling the analytics are described in detail in section 0.

Table 54: List of compounds and MS transitions for broad PFAS range method (CSIC_2).

#	Compound acronym	Retention time in min	ESI +/-	Precursor m/z	Fragment 1 m/z	Fragment 1 CE in V	Internal Standard (IS) acronym	Precursor m/z & quantifier	IS quantifier fragment CE in V
1	PFBA	0.54	-	212.9792	169	30	MPFBA	214.0612	30
2	PFPeA	0.83	-	262.9760	219	30	M5PFPeA	268.386	30
3	PFHxA	1.5	-	312.9728	269	30	M5PFHxA	318.3828	30
4	PFHpA	3.48	-	362.9696	319	30	M4PFHpA	367.2976	30
5	PFOA	5.15	-	412.9664	369	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
6	PFNA	5.94	-	462.9632	419	30	M9PFNA	472.7012	30
7	PFDA	6.70	-	512.9600	469	30	M6PFDA	519.45203	30
8	PFUnA	7.3	-	562.9568	519	30	M7PFUnDA	570.5308	30
9	PFDoA	7.76	-	612.9536	569	30	MPFDoA	614.0356	30
10	PFTTrDA	8	-	662.9504	619	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
11	PFTeDA	8.5	-	712.9472	669	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
12	PFHxDA	10.8	-	812.9408	769	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
13	PFODA	12.0	-	912.9344	869	30	M2PFTeDA	665.1144	30
14	PFBS	0.9	-	298.9429	80	30	M3PFBS	302.1889	30
15	PFPeS	2.8	-	348.9397	80	30	M3PFBS	302.1889	30
16	PFHxS	3.92	-	398.9366	80	30	M3PFHxS	402.1826	30
17	PFHpS	4.5	-	448.9334	80	30	M3PFHxS	402.1826	30
18	PFOS	6.12	-	498.9302	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
19	PFNS	6.8	-	548.9270	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
20	PFDS	7.1	-	598.9238	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
21	PFDoS	8.2	-	698.9174	80	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
22	FOSA	7.35	-	497.9462	78	30	M8FOSA	506.6022	30
23	4:2 FTSA	1.81	-	326.9742	307	30	M2-4:2FTS	329.1382	30
24	6:2 FTSA	5.21	-	426.9679	407	30	M2-6:2FTS	429.1319	30
25	8:2 FTSA	6.77	-	526.9615	507	30	M2-8:2FTS	529.1255	30
26	10:2 FTSA	8.2	-	626.9551	607	30	M2-8:2FTS	529.1255	30
27	6:2 diPAP	5.6	-	788.9750	97	30	M4-6:2diPAP	793.3030	30
28	8:2 diPAP	6.1	-	988.96227	543	30	M4-8:2diPAP	993.29027	30
29	ADONA	3.22	-	376.9688	251	30	M4PFHpA	367.2976	30
30	EtFOSA	6.7	-	525.9775	169	30	M8FOSA	506.6022	30
31	EtFOSAA	6.85	-	583.9829	419	30	d-N-EtFOSAA	584.9903	30
32	FOSAA	6.5	-	555.95168	419	30	d-N-MeFOSAA	570.9747	30
33	MeFOSAA	6.72	-	569.9673	419	30	d-N-MeFOSAA	570.9747	30
34	MeFOSA	6.2	-	511.9618	169	30	M8FOSA	506.6022	30
35	HFPO-DA (Gen-X)	0.8	-	328.96772	285	30	MGenX	330.0497	30
36	PFMOAA	0.6	-	178.9773	-	-	MGenX	330.0497	30
37	PFMOPrA	0.7	-	228.9741	-	-	MGenX	330.0497	30
38	PFMOBA	1.1	-	278.9709	-	-	MGenX	330.0497	30
39	PFO2HxA	2.1	-	244.9690	85	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
40	PFO3OA	3.4	-	310.9607	85	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
41	PFO4DA	5.1	-	376.9524	85	30	M8PFOA	421.6224	30
42	9CI-PF3ONS	4.8	-	530.8955	351	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30
43	11CI-PF3OUdS	6.9	-	630.8891	451	30	M8PFOS	507.5862	30

3.5.2. Material & Equipment

This section is equal to water samples analysis for CSIC_1 method (see section 0).

3.5.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Collection

The sample are collected with caution, to avoid any contamination and by using aluminium foil or PP tubes to preserve the samples and transported to the laboratory under cool conditions.

Sediment samples:

These samples use to be dried under fume cupboard till dryness before to preserve them at room temperature under dark conditions.

Lettuce samples:

This type of sample is preserved at - 20 °C until analysis.

In Lab Sample Preparation

Lettuce samples are defrosted, 2 g settled in a PP tube and spiked with 10 µl of extraction internal standards mixture (to have a final concentration of 20 ng/ml in vial). In the case of sediment samples, 0.5 g are introduced in a PP tube and spiked with the same amount of IS.

Calibration standards

The calibration used is the same as described for water samples for CSIC (see section 0).

Extraction/Enrichment

Sediments:

10 ml of pure methanol are introduced in the 50 ml PP tubes, shake vigorously for 5 min in a vortex and then extracted in an ultrasonic bath (USAE) for 1 h. Then, the sample is centrifuged at 4000 rpm at 20°C for 10 min. The supernatant is introduced in a new 50 ml PP tubes and dried near to 1 ml under nitrogen current. Then, 49 ml of ultra-pure water are used to dilute the sample before SPE clean up according to protocol described in Table 24.

Lettuce:

10 ml of NaOH (10 mM) in methanol are introduced in the 50 ml PP tubes, shake vigorously for 5 min in a vortex and then extracted in an orbital digester for 2 h. Then, the sample is centrifuged at 4000 rpm at 20°C for 10 min. The supernatant is introduced in a new 50 ml PP tubes and dried near to 1 ml under nitrogen current. Then, 49 ml of ultra-pure water are used to dilute the sample before SPE clean up according to protocol described in Table 24.

3.5.4. Analysis

The chromatographic separation of the compounds is carried out using liquid chromatography equipped with a Hypersil GOLD PFP column (50 x 3; from Thermo Scientific™) under gradient conditions with methanol (20 mM NH₄Ac) and water (20 mM NH₄Ac) with a 10 µL injection volume. The chromatographic system is coupled to an HRMS QExactive-Orbitrap analyser equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in negative. Data acquisition is by exact mass in full scan mode at a resolution power of 70,000 measured at full width at half maximum (FWHM) and, in parallel, in data dependent scan of the most intense ions, acquired at a resolution of 17,500 (FWHM) that provides the MS² confirmation. The data processing is through Xcalibur 3.0 software. The parameters considered for the identification of the PFASs are the exact mass, the fragmentation pattern in MS² when necessary and the retention time compared to the patterns of the pure standard compounds.

3.5.5. Performance

The method limits of quantification are summarized in Table 55.

Table 55: MLOQ for sediments and plants (lettuce) for the CSIC_2 method.

	Sediments (µg/Kg)	Plants (lettuce) (µg/Kg)
PFBA	1.41	0.07

PFPeA	0.50	0.04
PFHxA	0.53	0.23
PFHpA	0.36	0.36
PFOA	0.22	0.26
PFNA	0.13	0.26
PFDA	1.39	0.50
PFUnA	1.21	0.91
PFDoA	1.68	1.68
PFTrDA	1.68	2.52
PFTeDA	1.44	2.72
PFHxDA	2.08	0.52
PFODA	4.96	9.92
PFBS	0.31	0.16
PFPeS	0.25	0.08
PFHxS	0.10	0.39
PFHpS	0.40	0.90
PFOS	0.37	0.74
PFNS	0.89	0.37
PFDS	0.60	0.69
PFDoS	1.09	2.30
FOSA	0.80	1.05
4:2 FTSA	1.00	0.25
6:2 FTSA	1.00	0.13
8:2 FTSA	1.00	0.75
10:2 FTSA	2.00	1.25
6:2 diPAP	5.00	0.20
8:2 diPAP	5.00	2.00
ADONA	7.00	1.13
EtFOSA	4.30	0.35
EtFOSAA	4.00	0.15
FOSAA	3.10	0.10
MeFOSAA	5.00	0.40
MeFOSA	5.00	0.05
HFPO-DA (Gen-X)	6.00	0.63
PFMOAA	Not yet determined	Not yet determined
PFMOPrA	Not yet determined	Not yet determined
PFMOBA	Not yet determined	Not yet determined
PFO ₂ HxA	Not yet determined	Not yet determined
PFO ₃ OA	Not yet determined	Not yet determined
PFO ₄ DA	Not yet determined	Not yet determined

3.6. Stack Emission (ACEA_3)

3.6.1. Goals

Validated measurement methods are limited and under development for reliably identifying and quantifying if per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are released into the air from stationary sources. The current lack of standardized methods to measure PFAS emissions and the limited availability of data on the performance of methods to measure PFAS introduce uncertainty in the

understanding of the release of PFAS into the air from these sources. The lack of validated stationary source measurement methods for PFAS also leads to inconsistent findings, incomparable measurements, and lack of coordination between policy makers, facilities and control technology development.

The development of an analysis method for the determination of PFAS from the treatment residues of spent air from a pyrolysis process requires the availability of very specific samples. Particularly, the environmental matrix for the development of this analytical method can be generated only during laboratory experiments at UNIVPM laboratory. Indeed, there are no available full-scale pyrolysis plants that treat sewage sludge and RO concentrate generated during landfill leachate treatments. In addition, the sampling system to trap PFAS from stack emission generated during pyrolysis experiments has been designed for the first time by UNIVPM during PROMISCES research activities.

The study of the removal of PFAS from sludge and concentrate is included in Task 4.4 (Technologies for landfill leachate treatment) of WP4 of PROMISCES project. During the first 18 months of the project, the pyrolysis reactor and the stack emission sampling system have been designed and installed at the laboratory by UNIVPM. Particularly, the pyrolysis reactor has been installed in December 2022. On the contrary, the sampling system for stack emission has been installed at the end of March 2023. In figure 1 are reported pictures of the pyrolysis reactor coupled with the stack emission sampling system installed at UNIVPM laboratory.

Figure 1: Pyrolysis reactor and stack emission sampling system installed at UNIVPM laboratory.

The only document available today reporting a method for the determination of PFAS in stack emission is the guide OTM-45 developed by US-EPA. Particularly, this document reports a SOP for the measurements of PFAS in the stack emissions generated during incineration of sewage sludges and wastes. However, stack emission generated by incineration contains gas and aqueous vapours. On

the contrary, stack emissions generated by pyrolysis contain tar and bio-oil along with syngas. Hence, the schematic of sampling system advised by the OTM-45 has been slightly modified by ACEA and UNIVPM by the addition of a pre-condensation phase and a trap to separate bio-oil and tar from the produced syngas. Indeed, the presence of bio-oil may significantly affect the further adsorption process of organic micropollutants by the resin XAD-2 (adsorbent material suggested in the guide OTM-45).

In the absence of available matrix on which to perform the method development tests, in this chapter some notes about the method OTM-45 developed by US-EPA to analyse PFAs in the stack emission from incineration processes are reported. Indeed, this document represents the state of the art available at the moment for the subsequent development of a method for the detection of PFAS in stack emissions generated during a pyrolysis process. The analytical procedure, which includes also the collection phase of the stack emission, will be described in Deliverable D4.6 (M38). This deliverable will offer comprehensive insights into the method employed for PFAS emissions analysis, ensuring clarity and reproducibility in the research process.

It is also noteworthy to highlight that the operation of the pyrolysis reactor and the collection of the stack emissions are very complex operations that cannot be performed in a short time but require a long time of experimental activities. Following the installation of the pyrolysis reactor, UNIVPM has been conducting preliminary tests to define a protocol for the operation and maintenance of the reactor, which is quite complex. Then, first tests with pyrolysis reactor will be focused only on the solid products of the pyrolysis process. Indeed, optimal operational conditions (temperature and time of the reaction, optimal mix between sludge and RO concentrate, etc.) need to be defined to assess the removal of PFAS from the solid part. Then, the production and separation of tar and bio-oil from stack emission needs to be investigated. In addition, the amount of produced stack emissions needs to be quantified for each experiment. It is highly important to define the minimum and maximum amount of produced stack emissions that can go through the adsorption material placed in the stack emission sampling system. Furthermore, the cost for the analysis of PFAS from stack emissions (including the cost of adsorbent material such as resin XAD-2) is very expensive, and the number of tests for the development of the analytical method needs to be optimized.

Hence, due to the complexity of this task, the deadline for method development of PFAS in stack-emissions needs to be aligned with the experimental activities planned in WP4, which will be concluded at M38. We will report and describe the development of the analytical method for PFAS determination in stack emissions (including the SOP) in the Deliverable D4.6 (deadline M38). Indeed, this document will report all results related to the treatment of sludge and concentrate by pyrolysis to remove PFAS.

Reference: EPA Test Method 45 - (OTM-45) Measurement of Selected Per- and Polyfluorinated Alkyl Substances from Stationary Sources

The analytical method imbedded in OTM 45 can support the development of the analytical method for the measurements of stack emissions generated during pyrolysis tests of sewage sludge and RO concentrate. Here, are some notes about PFAS extraction and measurements as suggested by the abovementioned document.

Applicability

OTM-45 is a performance-based method applicable to the collection and quantitative analysis of specific semivolatile (Boiling point > 100°C) and particulate-bound per and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) in air emissions from stationary sources. This method can also be used for the collection and recovery of ionic and covalent PFAS for nontargeted analysis (NTA) of PFAS compounds. Table 44 of this method lists the individual target analytes that have been evaluated for measurement by OTM-45.

Table 56: List of PFAS to be covered in the ACEA_3 method for stack emissions.

Abbreviated Name	Isotopic Pre- Extraction Pair	Abbreviated Name	Isotopic Pre- Extraction Pair
PFBA	¹³ C4-PFBA	PFDS	¹³ C4-PFOS
PFPeA	¹³ C5-PFPeA	PFDoS	¹³ C4-PFOS
PFHxA	¹³ C2-PFHxA	FOSA	¹³ C8-FOSA
PFHpA	¹³ C4-PFHpA	MeFOSA	d3-MeFOSA
PFOA	¹³ C4-PFOA	EtFOSA	d5-EtFOSA
PFNA	¹³ C5-PFNA	N-MeFOSE	d7-N- MeFOSE
PFDA	¹³ C2-PFDA	N-EtFOSE	d9-N-EtFOSE
PFUnDA	¹³ C2-PFUnDA	MeFOSAA	d3-MeFOSAA
PFDoA	¹³ C2-PFDoA	EtFOSAA	d5-EtFOSAA
PFTTrDA	¹³ C2-PFDoA	4:2 FTS	M2-4:2 FTS
PFTeDA	¹³ C2-PFTeDA	6:2 FTS	M2-6:2 FTS
PFHxDA	¹³ C2-PFHxDA	8:2 FTS	M2-8:2 FTS
PFODA	¹³ C2-PFDoA	10:2 FTS	M2-10:2 FTS
PFBS	¹³ C3- PFBS	ADONA ¹	¹³ C4-PFOS
PFPeS	¹³ C3-PFHxS or ¹³ C3-PFBS	HFPO-DA (GenX)	¹³ C3-HFPO-DA
PFHxS	¹⁸ O2-PFHxS or ¹³ C3-PFHxS	9Cl-PF3ONS (F-53B Major)	¹³ C4-PFOS
PFHpS	¹³ C4-PFHpA	11Cl-PF3OUdS (F-53B Minor)	¹³ C4-PFOS
PFOS	¹³ C4-PFOS	NFDHA	¹³ C5-PFHxA
PFNS	¹³ C4-PFOS	PFEESA	¹³ C3-PFBS

Summary of Method

This method identifies and determines the concentration in mass per unit gas volume sampled of specific PFAS compounds in source emissions. Gaseous and particulate bound target pollutants are withdrawn from the gas stream isokinetically and collected in the sample probe, on a glass fiber or quartz filter, on a packed column of adsorbent material and in a series of impingers. The target compounds are extracted from the individual sample collection media. The OTM-45 train results in four (4) discreet sample extract fractions for analysis. The extracts are analysed by LC-MS/MS in the MRM detection mode. Quantification of each analyte is calculated using the isotope dilution technique. For QC purposes, the percent recoveries of the pre-extraction standards are calculated using the integrated peak areas of pre-analysis standard(s), which are added to the final extract and function as traditional internal standards, exclusively applied to the pre-extraction standards. The use of pre-sampling standards added to XAD-2 collection media prior to sampling and analysed in the same manner as targeted PFAS compounds serves as an indication of the method's quantitative capture efficiency. This method is not intended to differentiate between target compounds in particle or vapor fractions. This method uses isotopically labelled standards to improve method accuracy and precision.

The system set-up of stack emission sampler that will be utilized in WP4 and will not use filter or impinger, but a device to condensate and trap the bio-oil fraction before the XAD-2 resin. The solid residue in the pyrolysis chamber is termed as bio-char.

The method will be extended as bio-oil and bio-char, taking some indication from EPA 1633-2022. The method DIN 38414-14 (S 14) has been not considered for PFAS in bio-oil and biochar matrices, because so far has been only applied for sludge, compost and soil sample until 13 selected PFAS. EPA 1633:2022 (draft December 2022) could be more attractive for bio-oil and biochar analysis.

3.6.2. Material & Equipment

For material, instruments, chemicals see Table 35, Table 36 and Table 37 in section 3.1.

3.6.3. Sample Handling & Standards

Sample Handling: to be defined

Standard as in “Solid waste matrices: sludge and contaminated and treated sediment (ACEA_1)”, see section 3.1.

3.6.4. Analysis

The analytical details are currently under determination.

3.6.5. Performance

Initial MDL Determination

Perform an MDL determination for each sample media fraction (filter, XAD-2, and impinger solution) following the requirements in 40 CFR Part 136 Appendix B. The MDL study establishes the lowest detectable concentrations for each sampling train fraction. Sample specific MDLs are reported inclusive of sample-specific dilutions, final volumes, aliquots, etc.

Estimated MDL is calculated from the lowest calibration point of 0,25 pg/μL. Estimated MDL is subsequently confirmed by spiking each media with native target compounds at the MDL and pre-extraction isotopic labelled standards at the concentration used to analyse field samples.

Demonstration of Precision.

The percent relative standard deviation (% RSD) of the concentrations from the replicate analyses (at least 7) must be less than 30 % for all method analytes.

Demonstration of Accuracy.

The average recovery (at least 7 replicates) for each analyte must be within a range of 70–130 %.

4. Summary

4.1. Method overview

This section provides an overall method overview for swift selections of suitable methods for a variety of analytical constraints/requirements, such as targeted matrix, sensitivity, PFAS of interest, and equipment. Comprehensively, the methods detailed in this document cover 57 different PFAS and 12 different types of matrices. Table 57 summarizes the matrices and PFAS in the methods detailed in this document.

The large set of PFAS compounds, matrices, and other analytical constraints logically required the participating laboratories to accept certain compromises during the method developments. Exemplary, only relatively expensive top-notch analytical equipment can reach the generally extremely low limits of quantification that are nowadays required to cover the demands of legislation and authorities.

In addition, the considerable number of isotopically labelled internal standards necessary to cover the large substance property range involves substantial financial commitments; we further note that labelled standards are not available for the full range of analytes.

Pursuing these considerations, we strongly emphasise that the substances encompassed within the acronym “PFAS” are not what is typically considered “a group of substances”. Rather, PFAS are a relatively loose “group of substance groups”, related only by the weak characteristic that they contain a certain number of fluorine moieties in an otherwise fully variable organic molecular framework.

Table 57: Matrix and PFAS overview as covered in the PROMISCES, by the different partners (ACEA, BWB, BRGM_IPGP, CSIC and TU Wien)

#		Category	CAS number	ACEA_1	ACEA_2	BRGM_IPGP_1	BRGM_IPGP_2	BWB_1	BWB_2	CSIC_1	CSIC_2	TU Wien_1	TU Wien_2
	Groundwater /Drinking water					x		x		x			
	Surface water					x		x	x	x		x	
	Treated wastewater					x		x	x	x		x	
	Raw wastewater								x	x		x	
	Soil /Sediment			x			x			x	x		
	Sludge			x			x			x	x		x
	Liquid waste by NF/RO treatment			x									
	Landfill Leachate				x					x		x	
	Process Water					x							
	Plants / Lettuce									x	x		
1	10:2 FTSA	FTSA	108026-35-3			x	x			x	x		
2	11Cl-PF3OUdS (8:2 Cl-PFESA)	Cl-PFESA	83329-89-9			x	x		x				
3	3:3 FTCA	FTCA	356-02-5			x	x						
4	4:2 FTS	FTSA	27619-93-8	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
5	5:3 FTCA	FTCA	914637-49-3			x	x						
6	6:2 diPAP	diPAP	407582-79-0			x	x						
7	6:2 FTAB	other (AFFE)	34455-29-3			x	x						
8	6:2 FTCA	FTCA	53826-12-3			x	x						
9	6:2 FTS (H4-PFOS)	FTSA	27619-97-2	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
10	7:3 FTCA	FTCA	812-70-4			x	x						
11	7HPFHpA	other	1546-95-8			x	x	x					

12	8:2 diPAP	diPAP	678-41-1			x	x						
13	8:2 FTCA	FTCA	27854-31-5			x	x						
14	8:2 FTS	FTSA	27619-96-1	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
15	8:2 FTUCA	FTUCA	70887-84-2			x	x						
16	8:3 FTCA (4H-PFUnDA)	FTCA	34598-33-9			x	x						
17	9Cl-PF3ONS (6:2 Cl-PFESA)	Cl-PFESA	73606-19-6			x	x	x	x			x	x
18	C6O4		1190931-41-9	x	x								
19	EtFOSA	FASA	4151-50-2			x	x						
20	FBSA	FASA	30334-69-1			x	x		x				
21	FHxSA	FASA	41997-13-1			x	x		x				
22	FOSA	FASA	754-91-6	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
23	FOSAA	FASAA	2806-24-8			x	x						
24	HFPO-DA (GEN X)	PFECA	13252-13-6	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
25	MeFBSA	FASA	68298-12-4			x	x						
26	MeFBSAA	FASAA	159381-10-9			x	x						
27	MeFOSA	FASA	31506-32-8			x	x						
28	Na-DONA	PFECA	2250081-67-3	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
29	N-EtFOSAA	FASAA	2991-50-6	x	x	x	x	x				x	x
30	N-MeFOSAA	FASAA	2355-31-9	x	x	x	x	x				x	x
31	P37DMOA	PFCA	172155-07-6			x	x			x	x		
32	PFBA	PFCA	375-22-4	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
33	PFBS	PFSA	29420-49-3	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
34	PFDA	PFCA	335-76-2	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
35	PFDoDA	PFCA	307-55-1	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
36	PFDoDS	PFSA	1260224-54-1	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		
37	PFDS	PFSA	2806-15-7	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
38	PFECHS	other	335-24-0			x	x						
39	PFHpA	PFCA	375-85-9	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
40	PFHpS	PFSA	21934-50-9	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
41	PFHxA	PFCA	307-24-4	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
42	PFHxDA	PFCA	67905-19-5			x	x			x	x		
43	PFHxS	PFSA	82382-12-5	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
44	PFHxSAm	other (AFFF)	50598-28-2			x	x						
45	PFNA	PFCA	375-95-1	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
46	PFNS	PFSA	98789-57-2	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
47	PFOA	PFCA	335-67-1	x	x	x	x	x.	x.	x	x	x	x
48	PFODA	PFCA	16517-11-6			x	x			x	x		
49	PFOS	PFSA	4021-47-0	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
50	PFPeA	PFCA	2706-90-3	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
51	PFPeS	PFSA	630402-22-1	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
52	PFTeDA	PFCA	376-06-7	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x
53	PFTrDA	PFCA	72629-94-8	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x
54	PFTrDS	PFSA	174675-49-1	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		
55	PFUnDA	PFCA	2058-94-8	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
56	PFUnDS	PFSA	441296-91-9	x	x	x	x	x					
57	PFPrS	PFSA	423-41-6			x	x						

4.2. Outlook

This document presents methods developed within the PROMISCES project for practical applications such as monitoring of the different case studies, experiments, and other tasks. While the highly practice-oriented approaches allow for relatively direct assessment of feasibility of these methods, calculation of limits of quantification will remain challenging due to the overall high complexity of samples, as PFAS-free matrices for laboratory validation are not available – nowadays, PFAS traces

occur nearly everywhere. Additionally, some matrices are highly variable in themselves – like sludge or industrial and urban wastewaters or matrices produced during remediation experiments. Thus, continuous and thorough application of the developed methods will have to prove the analytical performance (robustness, limits of quantification) under varied real conditions, based on a larger number of samples.

All participating laboratories have developed methods suitable for the respective lab/case study/work package needs. But considering the list of PFAS that are common between the different methods, the participating laboratories will implement cross-measurements/validation on matrices covered by several methods in the project to check repeatability, intra-laboratory comparability etc. The PROMISCES team will further exchange directly with structures of standardisation-oriented actions, such as PolMo, DIN, CEN, and EURACHEM, e.g. through the PollMo initiative ([Pollution Monitoring - EURAMET](#)) in which some partners are involved.

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